

AMDO TIBETAN FEMALE WORKERS IN GSHONG YUL COMMUNITY: LIVES AND MIGRANT LABOR

Bsod noms sgröl ma བསོད་ནམས་སྐྱོལ་མ།
(Suonan Zhuoma 索南卓玛)¹

ABSTRACT

This paper explores five illiterate Tibetan women's backgrounds and experiences while doing factory work, caterpillar fungus collection, and construction labor outside their homes and accounts of their lives in Gshong yul (Xiangyu) Village, Bis mdo (Wendou) Tibetan Township, Ya rdzi (Xunhua) Salar (Sala)² Autonomous County, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China. The five reports offer detailed and descriptive accounts encompassing marriage, discrimination, prejudice, and workplace living conditions. Their narratives reveal pronounced emotional ambivalence, while their experiences as migrant workers are marked by fear, hardship, and despair. They reflect on their struggle for autonomy through economic participation, a tension reflecting the complex adaptation strategies of illiterate Tibetan women in the process of modernization.

KEYWORDS

Gshong yul Village, Amdo, Qinghai, Tibetan women, illiteracy, labor, farming, migrant labor

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² In 2025, Xunhua County was the only autonomous Salar county in China, with a total population of 161,600, of which 6,3859 were Salar. Other ethnic groups in the county include Tibetans, Hui, and Han Chinese. In 2006, the State put the Salar ethnic group in the Special Plan for Supporting the Development of Ethnic Groups of Smaller Population Size. <http://www.xunhua.gov.cn/html/1998/135171.html>, 28 February 2025.

INTRODUCTION

Life stories of five Tibetan female workers from Gshong yul¹ (Xiangyu) Village, Bis mdo (Wendou) Tibetan Township, Ya rdzi (Xunhua) Salar (Sala) Autonomous County, Mtsho sngon (Qinghai) Province, PR China are presented. Gshong yul Village is located in the southwest of Bis mdo Township, twenty kilometers from Ya rdzi County Town. The village lies between 35°74' N and 102°37' E between the Rgya ri ma sngang and Stag lha khri mountains. It is also known as Srung yul² because the two mountains resemble tiger-headed creatures protecting the village. In 2023, Gshong yul Village had five tribes³ with seventy-five households and about 400 people.⁴

Local Village Background

The government divided Gshong yul Administrative Village into three communes (*gongshe*). The First and Second communes were in Gshong yul Village, and the third was in Ru ma byung (Rimaxiong) Village, five kilometers southwest of Gshong yul Village. The Sha ba and Yu mo tribes, with twelve and twenty-three households, respectively, in Ru ma byung Village had 180 people in thirty-five households.

Gshong yul Village had 1,391 *mu*⁵ of cultivated land. Nine hundred *mu* were irrigated, and the rest were rainfed. A complex geological structure characterized this alpine canyon landform.⁶ The village's traditional livelihood was based on agricultural production, supplemented by a few domestic livestock. Before 1980, barley, flax, potatoes, and soybeans were cultivated. Barley

¹ *Gshong* 'deep valley', *yul* 'place'.

² *Srung* 'protect', *yul* 'place'.

³ Household count for the tribes: eighteen (Gshong yul), fifteen (Dred tshang), fourteen ('Bar tshang), fifteen (Sha ba tshang), and thirteen (Ed bzhed).

⁴ Information provided by the village Communist Party Secretary.

⁵ One *mu* is one fifteenth of a hectare.

⁶ Xunhua Salar Autonomous County Local Records Compilation Committee (2017:50-51).

was the villagers' staple food. Barley production depended solely on natural rainfall, and yields were poor.¹ Households were largely self-sufficient. Barley cultivation slowly decreased with the introduction of wheat, canola, beans, and vegetables such as green onions, radishes, and pak choi (bok choy).

Traditional farming was characterized by human-animal coordination. Two cow-yak crosses pulled a plow from the third month of the Chinese lunisolar calendar year. When sowing, manure, ash fertilizers, and seed were cast. Two cow-yaks later pulled a rake to level the ground. In the fifth lunar month, villagers weeded by hand and diverted water from Klu mo thang and Brag sne nang valleys for irrigation four or five times. Women and children harvested in autumn. Villagers assisted each other by plowing the fields after harvest. Harvested barley and wheat were dried and cleaned in the sun, milled with donkeys or mules pulling a stone roller, sacked, and placed in storerooms. Potatoes and beans were placed in cellars.

Since the late 1990s, villagers have used seed planters, herbicides, pesticides, and commercial fertilizers. Combines harvested wheat and chopped wheat stalks into straw and collected it in metal containers. The chopped stalks were placed in storerooms and later used as livestock feed, bedding, and organic fertilizer.

Tractors transported grain and people from the fields to homes and from homes to the fields and were also used to plow. In addition, government-built concrete irrigation channels reduced irrigation time from seven or eight days to three to four days. These developments increased wheat yields to 300-400 kilograms per *mu*.

The limited carrying capacity of alpine pastures encouraged animal husbandry. Before the 2010s, a household typically owned about five head of cow-yak crosses, twenty to thirty sheep, donkeys, swine, and one or two mules. The local cow-yak crosses were used in farming work; to produce meat,

¹ According to the village Party Secretary, barley yield was 150-200 kilograms per *mu* before the 1980s.

milk, butter, and yogurt, and were sold when needed to supplement family income. Piglets were bought and raised for household meat consumption. In 2025, the village had one private goat raiser and a livestock center¹ engaged in cattle and sheep breeding and sales.

In addition, villagers logged a forest on a hillside southwest of Gshong yul Village. Before the government officially closed and managed the forest in 1959, villagers cut timber to build houses and sell. In the 1980s, locals secretly cut trees and sold logs for ten to twenty RMB each, depending on size. Herbs collected and sold to local Salar businessmen included *Gentiana macrophylla* Pall, *Stellera chamaejasme* L, *Polygonum viviparum* L, *Thalictrum* 'Meadow-rue', and ferns.

Most residents sold their livestock because they lacked time to care for them after they began engaging in *zhor las* 'migrant labor'.

Certain government policies encouraged locals to engage in *zhor las* 'migrant labor', including Reform and Opening-up (1978), Western Development (2000), Supporting Ethnic Minorities with Smaller Populations (2005), and Constructing a New Socialist Countryside (2005). In 2019, the government invested one million RMB in developing rural tourism projects to build dams, arch bridges, pavilions, hotels, and restaurants in villages with scenic views in Bis mdo Township. The government recruited many locals to work in construction temporarily, which did not solve long-term employment issues.

¹ Yulong Cattle and Sheep Breeding Factory.

LITERATURE REVIEW

AMDO TIBETAN FEMALE IDENTITY

Social structure, family roles, religious beliefs, and economic activities have historically shaped A mdo Tibetan women's identity. Patriarchy powerfully influenced women in public and domestic spheres. Girls typically learned domestic skills and performed household chores as instructed by family female elders before marriage and generally received little encouragement to pursue education or enter nunneries to pursue religious studies. Immediate family members generally arranged marriages, with women joining their husbands' families after marriage. Married women typically shouldered primary responsibility within the family unit for domestic duties, childcare, and eldercare (Tseyang and Dhondup 2008, Wu 2013, Campbell 2020, Duo 2024).

Women also played pivotal roles in milking and other dairy work, weaving, and planting, making substantial economic contributions. As Buddhists, A mdo Tibetan women actively engaged in religious activities, e.g., daily religious rituals such as rotating prayer wheels, making offerings in their homes and communities, chanting religious texts, and fasting. These women's traditional, multi-faceted identity is complex and constrained by conventional gender roles as they play important roles in family, community, and economic activities (Zhang 1992).

The majority of women's contributions to household and agricultural production labor ensured the family's basic production and livelihood, thereby playing a critical role in keeping men in the workforce (Guo, 2009). However, with the surge in income-earning employment, women became increasingly engaged in the labor market. (Rajan, 2016; Duojie, 2020). They were no longer only responsible for domestic chores but also had a role outside the home. Their identity is not confined to the family but extends to their participation in the labor market as female workers.

Scholarly projects and perspectives on Tibetan women have examined Chinese communist nationalism, Tibetan nationalism, and Western feminism. However, each viewpoint has its own biases and limits in depicting Tibetan women, given the complexity of Tibetan society and the intricate interactions between various elements impacting women's life (Makley 1997). A more nuanced understanding of Tibetan women's experiences is achieved by placing them in specific regional, class, and religious contexts. This approach aims to avoid essentialism and to see women as active subjects of discourse rather than passive objects.

TIBETAN RURAL MIGRANT WORKERS

Tibetan rural migrant workers, as the name implies, are Tibetans who predominantly live in Tibetan rural areas, speak Tibetan, and practice Tibetan Buddhism. They often leave their homeland to pursue non-agricultural economic opportunities, primarily in the service, catering, and construction industries (Fischer 2011, Duojie 2024). These sectors are characterized by high labor intensity, significant workforce density, and low skill levels (Ma 2012, Wang 2014, Sun 2015, Sun 2016, Waner 2018, Dunzhu 2019). Tibetan rural migrant laborers in the A mdo region of Qinghai are of Tibetan ethnicity, predominantly speak the A mdo Tibetan dialect and Qinghai Chinese dialect as a second language. They typically are Tibetan Buddhists and have received limited formal education. Their labor patterns are often shaped by family and gendered dynamics, with male family members and spouses frequently working together. More A mdo males seek employment outside the home compared to women.

Most employment opportunities Tibetan rural migrant workers learn about are from friends and relatives working in A mdo, Khams, Dbus gtsang, and capital cities such as Chengdu (Sichuan) and Zi ling (Xining), Qinghai. These workers are at the lower end of the employment industry chain in labor-intensive sectors, including construction. Their roles are interwoven

within the farming production cycle and are often characterized as short-term, seasonal work (Guan 2015; Wang 2014).

Research on Tibetan female labor groups has concentrated on kinship and social status concerns. Zhang (2009) focused on the development of Lha sa carpet factories from the 1960s to the early 2000s, detailing the marginalization of Tibetan women weavers in the post-socialist period due to the intersection of patriarchy, ethnicity, and capital accumulation. In addition, research by Yang (2007) and Kang (2006) in Gannan Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture found that the experience of working outside the home had a positive impact on women and their families, enabling them to enhance their knowledge, broaden their horizons, and strengthen their self-awareness and self-esteem. Moreover, their earnings improved their family's financial standing and increased women's decision-making power, moving the traditional husband-wife dynamic toward equality.

However, Dala Duo's (2024) study of female migrant laborers in Chu ka Village, Reb gong (Tongren) City Town, Qinghai yielded a different conclusion. He found that women's increased economic income did not significantly improve women's status or decision-making power in the household. Women continued to be primarily responsible for their dual roles of production and reproduction, suggesting that traditional gender norms and the ethic of caregiving remained resistant to change. This highlights that the impact of work on Tibetan women is complex, and the narrative that economic activity improves women's status is oversimplified. As Rajan (2016) highlighted, a more nuanced understanding of how urbanization and modernization affect women's lives is required, given the complex and sometimes contradictory ways these processes impact individuals.

The present study situates Tibetan women within the broader context of urban-rural migration in Tibetan regions. It begins an investigation into the limited impact of collective labor patterns on women's familial and social status. Limitations in previous studies include a dearth of detailed case studies on

specific experiences of female migrant workers and failure to systematically investigate issues such as gender, identity, and survival of female migrant workers during the migration process. This paper aims to fill gaps in existing research by focusing on the individual narratives of Tibetan female migrant workers from a micro and gender perspective, enhancing the practical comprehension of Tibetan migrant labor gender dynamics.

CONSULTANTS

Five life stories of Tibetan women from Gshong yul Village are presented. Lha mo (b. 1994), Mtsho mo (b. 1988), Sgrol ma (b. 1983), and Bde skyid (b. 1970) married and moved into Gshong yul Village. Me tog (b. 1969) was born and grew up in Gshong yul Village. None of the women attended public schools.

I used semi-structured interviews with questions to understand why, how, when, and whom they worked with and their ideas about work, family, marriage, and themselves. Our conversations occurred during the 2023 Lunar New Year in Gshong yul Village. I am a local woman and conducted the interviews in A mdo Tibetan. They trusted me and felt free to answer my questions.

Their ages, thoughts and experiences are authentic but I changed their names to protect their privacy.

ACCOUNT ONE: Lha mo (b. 1994)

I started working when I was fifteen. My mother's sister ran a restaurant near Nepal. I was asked to help because they were short of staff, so I went with my aunt. I don't remember the town's name. I only remember many big mountains, and the pleasant climate was neither particularly hot nor cold. The leaves were green all year round. It was a border area. One side was China, and the other side was Nepal. Soldiers guarded both sides, and a bridge was in the middle. You had to show your passport to go from one country to another. I could see the houses, the people, and everything on the other side, but I had no passport, so I couldn't cross the border.

The restaurant was simple. Four or five local young women worked there as servers. I couldn't understand them, so I tried to learn the local language. Aunt arranged for me to do the accounts in the restaurant. China and Nepal's currencies differed, so I suffered a lot doing the accounts. Nepalese often ate in our restaurant. The customers laughed at me for being an idiot when I miscalculated the money or communicated poorly. My aunt was temperamental and scolded me severely whenever I made mistakes.

I didn't go home for two years for Lo sar 'Tibetan New Year'. I had no friends and was bored and lonely every day, especially when I was homesick. I called my mother and complained that I didn't want to stay. She agreed, so I returned home with one of my uncles. I don't know how much my aunt paid me because she gave it to my mother.

When I returned home, I assisted my mother with household chores and farming. I married two years later and moved into my husband's home. My mother and brother arranged the marriage. I inwardly refused when I learned I would marry a man I had never met. Still, when I thought that my father had passed away when I was eleven and that my mother and brother had worked hard to rear me, I did not refuse the marriage. I naively thought that if I listened to my mother and worked hard to be a good daughter-in-law in my husband's home, I would live a happy life. However, the reality was harsh.

I was pregnant a year later. My ex-husband's parents were incredibly nice to me, didn't urge me to do a lot of work every day, and didn't force me to go out to work to earn money. Instead, they advised me to stay home and rest. My husband was a truck driver and often away from home. He returned only once or twice a month. I was bored with my in-laws. Sometimes, I felt lonely when I couldn't fit in with their family, so I contacted my cousin and went to work with her in Hongqi Salar Village in Salar srang (Jiezi) Town for a Salar family building a new house. We ate and lived in their house.

I was five months pregnant. Luckily, my work was not very heavy. I was an assistant laborer.¹ The only demanding thing I did was to follow workers to move wood and bricks. When I sat in a trailer pulled by the tractor, it was tough to move around. I was afraid my belly would strike something. Female workers who knew I was pregnant protected me in the trailer. After working for over a month, the boss saw my belly getting bigger and advised me to go home.

After giving birth to my son, I was pregnant again the following year. My husband was often away from home, and I didn't want to face my parents-in-law alone, so I chose to work with my cousin again, building a new restaurant for a Muslim. I was assigned to carry rocks needed for the foundation. After the truck driver brought a load of rocks, the excavator operator was responsible for unloading them. My cousin, three female Chinese laborers, and I were responsible for putting rocks into holes in the ground to create the restaurant foundation. At first, my boss didn't know I was pregnant. After I had worked for a week, my boss found out and was worried because he didn't want to take responsibility if something happened to me. He advised me to go home. Several other workers also told me to go home and have my baby instead of working there.

However, I desperately didn't want to leave. I wanted to stay and have something to do, have company, and be free, so I pleaded

¹ Assistant-workers generally mix concrete, carry building materials (rebar, bricks, etc.), carry buckets, assist men install pipes and cables, and other tasks.

with my boss to allow me to stay. He reluctantly agreed that I would leave after working for a month.

I was careful to avoid rocks slipping when I carried them. I used my hands to ensure the rocks did not press my belly. After I had worked for a month, the boss paid me 3,600 RMB (120 RMB a day). When I started to go home, my cousin bought me a ticket and escorted me to the bus. I was grateful she also bought meat and fruit for me.

I did not resent my in-laws because I was pregnant and working. My mother-in-law said, "You are pregnant. You should exercise. If you lie down, rest at home every day, and eat nutritious meals, the baby will absorb too many nutrients and become very big. You won't be able to give birth because the baby will weigh too much. The baby is in the womb and will grow normally as long as you don't crush or hurt him with stones."

When I returned to my ex-husband's home, my mother-in-law encouraged me to walk and exercise so I wouldn't lie in bed. I went to the *ma Ni khang*¹ every day to circumambulate and did chores and farm work that didn't hurt my belly. It was all fine, and there was less pain when I gave birth.

My husband was rarely with me during the two years when I was pregnant. When I learned from my relatives and friends that he had a girlfriend and often smoked, drank, gambled, wandered, and was caught stealing, I felt there was no hope for me in that family. I felt I was just a tool for his children and a caretaker for his parents. Though I had two children and my parents-in-law were very nice to me, I didn't want to stay, so I told my mother and brother I wanted to get a divorce. They agreed.

After the divorce, I returned to my natal home where my mother, brother, sister-in-law, and their two children lived. Neither my brother nor my sister-in-law attended school. They lived by farming, collecting caterpillar fungus, and earning money through construction work. To help my brother share the family's burden, I worked in a factory in Suzhou City, Jiangsu Province, after the

¹ A place where villagers perform religious activities, circumambulate, prostrate, and chant scriptures.

harvest with four young village women of the same age. The township government introduced the job to us. The village clerk told us the job didn't require educational qualifications as long as we could speak Chinese and communicate with the boss. We visited a factory that manufactured cell phones. It was my first time in a Chinese city.

We arrived in the ninth lunar month, and the weather was very hot. We were a group of five women. Two knew some Chinese, so I just followed them. It was a large factory. The team leader placed the five of us in different workshops. We each had a card and swiped it when we went to work, during security checks, and for meals. Our wages were credited to this card.

Our work schedules were different. I was scheduled from six p.m. to three a.m. and put a QR code on cell phones that passed on a conveyor belt through the hands of about fifty people before reaching me. I used tweezers to remove a QR code prepared in advance and stuck it on the back of the phone. Every workshop had a supervisor. We were not allowed to chat while working and had to wear overalls. When I needed to use the bathroom, I had to inform the supervisor, who then arranged for another person to take my place.

The factory had workshops, canteens, dormitories, and shops. We ate in a crowded cafeteria and had to wait in line for a long time. I ate eggs, pickled mustard tuber, and porridge in the morning. There were various vegetables and noodles at noon and in the evening. The five of us ate cheap meals to save money. I saw some Chinese women eating in the restaurant, but we did not. We lived in the factory women's dormitory. Ten people were in a room with bunk beds. Five of us Tibetan women lived with five Chinese women. We worked in that factory for three months. I was paid fifteen RMB an hour, and the company paid us at the end of each month.

Work varied. The longer you stayed, the higher your salary. If you wanted to work overtime, the relationship between you and your boss was the determining factor. The five of us stayed together except during work hours. I wasn't bored.

I was nervous and anxious every day because my Chinese is poor. Whenever the team leader assigned tasks to me, I was concerned that I wouldn't understand, so I was always alert. I was worried the boss would dismiss me if I did a poor job. I was cautious. Sometimes, when the team leader scolded me, I dared not reply. A girl from a herding area in Sichuan Province had gone to school and was very bold. When the team leader scolded her, she quarreled with him. She was not afraid of him, unlike timid me. When a Chinese woman in the dormitory laughed at us for not speaking standard Mandarin, I was angry and said, "We grew up speaking Tibetan. Chinese is very difficult for us to learn. Would it be easy to learn if you were asked to speak Tibetan?"

A friend introduced my second husband. We often communicated on WeChat, and then we stayed together. I now have two sons with him. My ex-husband's family raised my son from my first marriage while I kept my daughter. My brother had two children. He and his wife wanted another child. After I cared for my daughter for six months, I gave her to them. My daughter calls them "mother" and "father" and thinks I'm her sister. My brother and sister-in-law treat her like their daughter, often buy her new clothes and toys, and take extra good care of her. I'm happy for her. After I married into my second husband's family, I often went out to work with him.

My current parents-in-law are traditional farmers who earn a living from a small amount of farmland, collecting caterpillar fungus, and working outside. A year after I married into their home, I went to Gser rta (Seda) County, Dkar mdzes (Ganzi) Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, Sichuan Province, with my husband and parents-in-law to work in 'Brong ri Monastery, where my husband and his parents had been working for two years. I heard that an uncle of my husband's helped locate this job. We worked as assistant workers. Each of us was paid 120 RMB a day. We worked there for two months, carrying stones, building foundations with rocks, and so forth. The workers were local Tibetans and Chinese. My parents-in-law decided not to leave the village to work because many villagers were building new houses then. My husband and father-in-law were also thinking of doing the same, so a decision

was made that my husband and I would go out and earn money while my parents-in-law would take care of the children and the farm.

Although we are farmers, we can't only make money by farming. We grow only enough crops to feed ourselves. We must provide for our children in school, support our parents, buy a car, build a new house, and the village headman often collects money. For example, every family paid a few hundred RMB last year to make a village square. The village headman collects a fine if no family member attends the community *ma Ni* hall to chant during religious activities.

My husband and I have tried many ways to earn an income. We collected caterpillar fungus in Rma stod (Maduo) County, Mgo log Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture. Each collector paid 10,000 RMB. Neither of us could find many, so we lost money that time. My husband is careless. How can he find caterpillar fungus when he sometimes can't even find what's in front of him?!

After losing money, we were ashamed to go home, so we planned to find a job in Mgo log Prefecture Town. We stayed in a small hotel for three days but didn't find work. In desperation, my husband and I went to Zi ling City. After two days, one of my husband's friends introduced us to a man in Na gor mo (Ge'ermu, Golmud) City, Haixi Mongol and Tibetan Autonomous Prefecture, who needed grass planters. He asked if we would like to go. We immediately agreed. When we arrived, we realized that the place was desert. There was not a single tree. Especially in the seventh lunar month, we felt it was hot as Hell. We lived in a tent and couldn't bear the temperature after work each day. It felt like we were in a steamer. During the day, we had to go to the desert to plant grass. Walking, we would get stuck in the sand, and our feet would get extra hot. Sometimes, sand got in our eyes and mouths when the wind blew.

After half a month, we couldn't bear the climate, so we gave up and returned to Zi ling. When we arrived, one of my husband's uncles introduced us to a job planting pine trees in Brag dkar (Xinghai) County that paid 130 RMB a day per person. The other workers were all local herders who came to work in the morning and left in the evening. I prepared breakfast, lunch, and dinner for about

twenty people. I soon became pregnant. My parents-in-law learned this and insisted I return home.

Collecting caterpillar fungus is a risky endeavor, so my husband and I decided to learn a new skill. My husband's friend recommended we go to a restaurant in Lhasa City. We signed a three-month contract with the boss stipulating that she would deduct 1,000 RMB from our salary of 4,000 RMB per person if we left early. We ate and lived in that little restaurant, which served A mdo noodles and other noodle dishes. There were ten tables, and business was good with a steady daily stream of customers. The daily income was about 10,000 RMB.

That job was tough. There were five of us with the owner, the owner's wife, and their son. I had to get up at six a.m. every day. Until eleven a.m., I washed and chopped vegetables – fifty kilograms of chili, zucchini, and so on. My husband was responsible for kneading the dough and making it into various shapes. The boss ordered us to have it ready by eleven a.m. After that, we could have breakfast. The boss was mean and gave us a small amount of poor-quality food. By noon, there were many customers. Many thought the A mdo noodles were delicious. The business was perfect. Other restaurants used machines to make noodles. However, the owner insisted it was better to make them by hand, so my husband, the owner's wife, and I pulled the noodles by hand. I felt my hands were going to break when there were forty customers. It was midnight when I finished washing all the dishes. The boss's wife would then tell me to cut the meat for the next day and clean. It was one a.m. when I could finally rest.

After two and a half months, my husband received a message from his father that one of his uncles had passed away and asked him to hurry home to attend the funeral. My boss's wife was unhappy and took her anger out on me. When I said I wanted a good meal, the boss's wife sarcastically said I was asking for too much. Sometimes, she scolded me for laziness when I took an extended break and threatened to dock my wages. When I thought about this, I didn't want to keep working and told my boss's wife I was quitting.

She angrily deducted 1,000 RMB from each of us because we were leaving early. She said, "You can go to court and sue me if you two don't accept this."

I knew I was wrong and said nothing. As I got ready to go home, I couldn't even buy a ticket online. No one could help, so I had to ask the owner's wife. She was reluctant to let me go because they couldn't find a server quickly, and their business was good.

My husband and I didn't want to work there. We slept on cramped wire beds and couldn't eat on time every day. There was also endless work to do. After I begged my boss to buy my ticket, he drove me to the train station. I took the train back to Zi ling alone. I didn't know how to read Chinese, so I had to ask others for help. I met some Chinese workers at the train station who were going to Zi ling. They helped me and I was very grateful.

I transferred to a bus to Xunhua County when I got to Zi ling.

This was the first time I took a train by myself, so I felt I was good at speaking Chinese, though I didn't recognize Chinese characters. If I hadn't gone out to work and had experience in learning Chinese, I wouldn't have been able to find a train station. Now that my Chinese is slightly better, I'm not scared to go to a big city alone.

After working in a restaurant, my husband and I were naive enough to think that we could open a restaurant and make a lot of money, so we rented a restaurant in Gcig sgril (Jiuzhi) County, Mgo log Prefecture. We lost money after six months of operation. The county is small. I saw few people on the street, and herders didn't want to eat A mdo noodles. However, a noodle shop run by a Xunhua Salar couple was doing well. They said they had been in business for many years.

After losing money, we were afraid to do business again.

A regular job is the only way for both of us. There is no risk or worry like collecting caterpillar fungus or running a restaurant. Just finish the day's work and get paid. In the past three years, we have been in Zi ling City looking for construction work. Unlike herding areas in winter, where the land freezes and stops work, year-round employment in Zi ling meant we each earned almost 60,000 RMB a year.

At the beginning of spring 2019, we visited Zi ling City to look for work at construction sites. Luckily, we found an easy job working as electrical line workers, installing lines in every apartment in a building. My husband was paid 180 RMB a day, and I was paid 160 RMB. About fifteen buildings were under construction. Each was thirty-two stories high. Many people were working on them. About thirty to forty people were team leaders, and 300 employees were under one team leader. We went to work in the morning. All the workers swiped their cards to enter the construction site. Many security guards were around us. Once we arrived at the workplace, the team leader assigned tasks for the day. The team leader usually separated my husband and me. I followed one worker, and my husband followed another. My tasks were to assist the worker with whatever they needed, including lifting tools, drills, cords, etc. If you worked overtime at night, you worked until two or three a.m.

Every day, I followed a different worker. When the worker was from Sichuan Province, I didn't understand his dialect when he asked me for something. He would then get angry, and I was too scared to ask him to repeat it.

When I met a better-tempered worker, they got their things independently and didn't scold me. You could rest only if the worker rested. Some workers bullied me, ordering me to do this and that when they found a chance to rest. I purposely didn't listen.

Once, when I was done with work and about to leave, two workers came and ordered me to get to work. I said I didn't have time and left, even though we knew each other well. They got angry, treated me poorly afterward, and often called me an idiot.

We had to work on our feet every day. We rarely sat. The supervisor wore a white hat and monitored us. He was responsible for determining if we were lazy and the work was done according to plan. He would take a photograph and send it to your team leader, who would reduce your salary if you were lazy or not doing a good job.

Fortunately, we never had an accident. I often reminded my husband to stay safe. We didn't sign a contract with the boss, so I took care of minor injuries myself. Major injuries were up to the boss to deal with. The team leader once arranged for me to ride a three-

wheeled electric scooter at night to carry items from the elevator to the upper floors. I knew it was dark and dangerous at night, so I refused. I had heard about a woman from Dp'a lung (Hualong) Hui Autonomous County who drove an electric cart to the elevator at night and fell to her death because it was dark and the elevator was unfinished.

Unpaid wages were worse. When we had worked for three months and were ready to go home to harvest, the contractor said there was no money in their project and would pay us when it became available. We had no choice but to go home and wait for a month. We called the boss daily, asking for the 20,000 RMB owed to us. We nearly sued them in court. Thankfully, the money was eventually paid. I heard that some workers didn't receive their money.

Whenever we went home, I fought with the employers instead of being happy with the money I had earned. We argued and urged them to pay us and went home in despair. So many painful memories. We worked hard for our money, but they dismissed us by saying there was no money. This money was the most critical income we had in a year.

Because of Covid-19 in 2022, many construction companies stopped, and my husband and I had difficulty finding work. At first, we got jobs in buildings under construction near the Zi ling Train Station. We were paid 200 RMB salary each per day and stayed in a painted metal room. I lived in the women's dormitory on the second floor.

Meals were the company's responsibility initially, but after a week, the boss said that we should deal with our food and that he would add twenty RMB a day to everyone's daily account. There were six workers. I followed them to the basement to remove old wires and bring new ones or hand them pliers and tape they asked for. Sometimes, there was not much to do, and the boss didn't constantly supervise you. We worked there for a month, though the outside of the Train Station was closed. When the epidemic became severe after two months, the company shut down.

At that time, all of Zi ling was blocked. We could not go home. We stayed in a cheap hotel, but it was not a solution, so we looked

for a job and finally found a job in a construction site next to Wanda Plaza pouring concrete on floor heating pipes. Due to the pandemic, we were only allowed to work at night and rest during the day, so we started at six p.m. The concrete was poured out of a black pipe from a truck. Two workers carried a heavy concrete pipe. Others held the head of the tube with a rope and poured the concrete onto the pipes. When we finished working, it was five to eight a.m. We slept in bunk beds in the company's metal room during the day. There were only four workers then. The boss couldn't find people due to the epidemic, so we four workers had to do all the work.

The boss was incredibly kind to us. We were each paid 280 RMB daily. After we had worked for ten days, the epidemic regulations became stricter, so we had to stop working. Two workers from Shanxi Province immediately packed their things and took the train home. My husband and I were unable to return home. We were stuck in the company's dormitory for more than twenty days.

We couldn't buy food and trusted our boss to buy something for us. We asked him to buy two boxes of instant noodles and a small electric cooker to save money. We slept until eleven a.m., so we didn't have to eat breakfast. When we got up, we cooked instant noodles in an electric cooker and ate. Luckily, a fellow villager ran a steamed bun shop in Zi ling. My husband begged him to send us some steamed buns and milk.

In the eleventh lunar month, the dormitory had no heating or sunlight. I could only sleep every day. I could not sleep without plugging in the electric blanket, which broke after I plugged it in repeatedly every day. My husband said it wasn't good for us to lie around every day, so we chanted and prayed the epidemic life would end.

Later, the boss left in a private car to his home. He was very generous. He left his pots and pans with us and gave us 200 RMB to buy food. We stuck around for a while after buying food with that money. We contacted some friends through cell phones and heard that some people had walked to Xunhua County from Zi ling. They said it took three days and three nights. When I thought about how cold it was in winter, I thought, "What if we freeze to death on the

road, get caught by the police, and have to pay a fine, or be forced into quarantine or something?"

We were afraid to go home. Our fellow villager who owned the bun shop advised us not to walk home. He suggested we rent a car to go home. My husband and I had a lot of work certificates at the construction site. After packing our things, we lived in the fellow-villager's shop with only one small room separated by a curtain. The fellow and his wife sold buns at the front counter while their two kids had internet classes on their cell phones behind the curtain. After selling buns, they packed their things for the next day's trip home.

The next day, we encountered many checkpoints on the road. Policemen would not let us pass, demanding that we have a certificate from Wendu Township certifying that we had the township government's consent. We had no choice but to call the company's owner and ask him to explain it to the policemen. Still, they wouldn't let us go, so we had no choice but to return to the shop where the couple busily made buns. We were very embarrassed to stay in the store.

I did not know when we could go home. That year, we only went home for six days to harvest the crops. I especially missed my two sons. When I thought about it, I was desperate and helpless. I cried all night. My husband and the couple comforted me, telling me not to worry too much, that everything would pass. After a day in the store, a friend called and said the road would be unblocked that night. We did not believe it, but after asking others, we realized it was true, so we said goodbye to the couple and left.

My husband said we might have to go to another city to look for jobs the next year because we felt it would be difficult to find work in Zi ling. The bosses look for men when you look for a job in Zi ling. They will ask women if they can read and speak Chinese. If you cannot, they consider if you are with your husband. If so, they accept you. If you look for a job alone, they won't accept you.

I have learned from my work experience that even if you are a woman who doesn't know Chinese characters, your boss will want you as long as you are hardworking and work seriously. Whenever I started a new job, I worked extra hard, so the boss believed in my

ability to work and liked me. He would then want to keep me on. I made earnest efforts to get the boss's affirmation. A boss never said I did not do a good job, nor was I fired. They all liked me, praised my work, and wanted me to remain on the job. For example, one boss arranged for me to work alone in a dark and scary basement. I was scared, but I never said I wouldn't go. I dared finish the job while looking behind me in fear.

Secondly, bosses will choose long-term workers over short-term workers. The bosses wouldn't want to hire us if we said we would stay two to three months. We understood that the bosses wanted long-term, reliable employees rather than always looking for new people. We said we were willing to work for a long time, but the truth was that we had to return home to help our family harvest, or something urgent made us leave. Finally, we lacked skills.

Last year, I met a Chinese man with his wife and parents. The man told me that the whole family earned 30,000 RMB a month, each had a skill, and they didn't go home for a year.

Bosses advised us that we won't make much money as laborers. It's a job with no future. I persuaded my husband to learn a skill, but he has no interest in construction and is unwilling to learn. I have no choice but to work and obey others' commands. My husband has a junior high school education. I do not. I would learn some skills if I knew how to read and write. But now I can only follow my husband to look for work. When I had to scan QR codes on my cell phone during last year's pandemic, I needed his help registering my information. He taught me how to write my name in Chinese characters.

All the money we earned was used to finish building two sides of a new house. The other two sides and the yard remain to be made. It cost more than 300,000 RMB to build this much of the house. My husband and I gave all our money to my father-in-law, who decided how the money would be used. Women like me love to buy new clothes and cosmetics, but I dared not allow myself such enjoyment. I was always concerned about saving money for the family. New Tibetan robes cost hundreds of RMB. If my husband doesn't buy one for me, I won't have the money to buy one. I usually buy clothes that cost fifty-sixty RMB. Last year, I secretly purchased

190 RMB of cosmetics. I didn't dare tell my husband and mother-in-law the real price. I lied and said they were fifty RMB. They wouldn't agree to spending money on expensive cosmetics.

When my husband and I work outside, we're cautious about buying our favorite fruits or eating in restaurants. Sometimes, we don't have any cash and must rely on our bosses to pay our salaries. I kept the money others gave my child during the New Year. I lacked pocket money. As a daughter-in-law, I'm supposed to be well-behaved, save all my money, and spend it on the family.

All women become daughters-in-law one day. My mother and brother chose my first in-laws and sent me to my husband's home with the idea that they would treat me like family, love me, and care for me. If your in-laws love and care about you, you must be grateful and return the favor. However, which daughter-in-law has no suffering?

My current mother-in-law and I live under one roof, and a little disagreement can be carried in my heart for a long time. My mother-in-law is very unreasonable. As long as I am at home, she does no chores and does not help me. If I argue with her, my husband is in the middle and helpless. I pity him. I don't say anything. I endure it. It's challenging for my parents-in-law to care for two children while working on the farm at home. I understand. I don't discuss family matters with people in the village. The village is so small that if I speak to others about my family matters, they gossip, and my mother-in-law will know about it.

I never say anything bad about my mother-in-law when I am in my natal home. It's not easy for my mother to be on her own. I don't want her to worry. I have no father, and my mother has no company. I wouldn't be so afraid of my in-laws if I had a father. My father would help me talk to my in-laws and say, "Please treat my daughter nicely."

If my family is happy, I will not feel miserable even if I go out to work. If my family is not harmonious, it will be more miserable for me as a daughter-in-law who must go out to work.

ACCOUNT TWO: Mtsho mo (b. 1988)

After arriving in Mgo log Prefecture Town at night, my husband and I heard that the local government and herders had set up many roadblocks to collect caterpillar fungus tax and restrict the flow of people from outside the area. If caught, you would be charged thousands of RMB in tax or banished from Mgo log Prefecture. However, some herders sought to profit from their grassy hills. After my husband and I paid a local herder almost 10,000 RMB, he agreed to clandestinely allow us to stay on his grassy hill in Snowy Mountain Township.

Nearly twenty of us sat in the back of the herder's big truck that night. Everyone wore headlamps. We all crammed in with our luggage. We were shaken like a load of hogs. The driver instructed us to disembark from the truck at each roadblock immediately, walk a short distance ahead, and then meet him at a designated place. He warned us to move quickly so we would not be caught. I don't know how long we sat in that bouncing, shaking truck. When it suddenly stopped, the driver exited and raced to us. He said his friend had been arrested at an intersection roadblock ahead of us. He told us to leave the truck quickly, walk to a mountain road junction, and be there because he would not wait for stragglers.

Everyone in the back of the truck began scrambling, pushing, and shoving to exit the truck after he finished speaking. Some people bumped into one another since it was so dark. I couldn't see if others were carrying their luggage. I held my duffel bag with food, cooking oil, noodles, spices, and meat. Everyone moved hectically and as fast as possible. I also carried a backpack while running. After reaching our destination, everyone hurriedly boarded the truck again. Some pushed and pulled me, hurting me.

The driver stopped the truck again and told us to get off. Others jumped out and marched together like before. Just as I was about to jump out of the truck, I was afraid my shoes would get wet, so I took them off. After crossing the stream by jumping and walking, I found it difficult to climb up the bank while carrying my backpack. Eventually, I made it. I was now weak.

I put on my shoes and got ready to run, but I couldn't find my socks. I knew I didn't have time to search for them. Looking around, I discovered that my husband was no longer with me. Afraid of getting lost, I ran desperately until I caught up with several Chinese. My shoes had heels, so I kept tripping. While following the Chinese, my husband suddenly appeared. He repeatedly said my name and pulled me. I was angry and wondered why he wouldn't wait for or accompany me. Wasn't he afraid that I would get lost? Afterward, I ignored him. He offered to take my bag but I did not give it to him. Still, he accompanied me as I walked, and I felt more at ease.

I don't remember how many times we got off and on the truck. I fell many times that night. As dawn approached, the driver instructed us to find a hiding spot during the day to avoid detection, promising to pick us up that night. Half of us spent the day under a bridge. It had snowed. There was ice and water. Everyone was tired from running all night and slept. I couldn't sleep because my feet were cold, so I removed my shoes and covered them with my hands to make them warmer. We ate buns and pickles we had brought. In the late afternoon, we contacted the driver. After he picked us up, we resumed our efforts to avoid checkpoints.

That night proved particularly challenging. It started raining heavily as we entered a dark, rugged valley. When the driver made another stop, we jumped out of the truck without our luggage and began walking to where the driver had indicated. One woman became too exhausted to continue walking. A few people pulled her. We climbed a hill. As we descended, a big river appeared before us. Our initial intention was to cross, but then we noticed a checkpoint and someone surveying the area with a flashlight. No one knew what to do. A man called the driver and asked what to do. The driver made fun of us, "You cowards should avoid the checkpoints by crossing the river."

We then had no choice. Despite the rain, some people walked across the river holding hands. The water reached their thighs. I held my husband's hand, and we waded across. Though we succeeded in crossing the river, our happiness was short-lived. Several tents blocked our path. I saw a man smoking inside a car.

As we snuck through the rain, he exited the vehicle. My heart raced in panic. Fortunately, he only returned to his tent with a flashlight. I exhaled deeply and continued crawling on my belly. We advanced, dodging checkpoints and climbing over wire fences, ensuring we were not being followed before stopping to rest. As we waited, I realized we were stuck in a tangle of buckthorn bushes. Our clothes and faces were covered with sea buckthorn juice, and we couldn't find a way out. After a night of running, everyone fell asleep in exhaustion. We had to remain hidden during the day and didn't dare go outside of the buckthorn bushes in fear someone might notice us. That day, my feet were cold despite covering them with my hands. When it got dark, the driver arrived to pick us up and took us to his family's grassy hill.

The landowner expressed surprise that we had avoided the checkpoints and offered to bring a group to his family's grassy hill the following day. We spent the night in their tent. The next day, we carried our bags to a location where we were less likely to be seen at checkpoints. I initially struggled to collect caterpillar fungus. It wasn't until four or five days later that I got used to the terrain that I began to make progress. We constantly collected caterpillar fungus, and when people from the checkpoints came looking for us, we had to elude them.

After twenty days, my husband and I decided to leave due to the unbearable conditions. We packed our bags, carried them from the mountain to the road, and hired a herdsman to transport us back to Mgo log Prefecture Town. A single caterpillar fungus sold for fifteen RMB at that time. After selling what we had tirelessly searched for, my husband and I were able to regain what we had spent to search the land. Ten thousand RMB remained. This was my first experience collecting caterpillar fungus with my husband. I was nineteen.

My husband's family had proposed marriage to me a year earlier when I was eighteen. My father accepted after drinking the liquor they had brought. I had never met my future husband and was reluctant to marry a stranger. That year, many villagers started going out to work. My father planned to follow some villagers to look for work. After the fall harvest, I begged my father to take me with

him, naively thinking that if I could earn money for my family, my parents would not have to marry me off.

My father, three other people from the same village, and I went to Zi ling City together. We found work at the railway station replacing old wooden ties in the railway tracks. We were arranged to live in a five-story workers' dormitory. The rooms were clean, and the cafeteria food was good. We had to get up at five a.m. and work in groups of five. Each person had to change five ties. The ties were heavy, and it was hard for women to lift a tie.

Our boss disliked women and often scolded us for our lack of strength. One day, my aunt got her finger caught in a wooden tie. The boss then declared women were a nuisance and forced my aunt and me to leave. We were paid thirty-five RMB a day and had worked for half a month.

My father and my aunt's husband continued working. We didn't want to go home so early, so my aunt suggested we find waitress jobs. I agreed. We applied to several restaurants, but only one, a particularly large hot pot restaurant in Ximen Mall, was willing to hire us. Aunt and I couldn't read Chinese and spoke only a little simple Chinese. The restaurant manager told us to clean the bowls of food after the customers left and stand in the lobby. Fifty restaurant attendants worked there, and most of them were women. We started at ten a.m. and finished at midnight. We got one day off a week. My aunt and I lived in a large dormitory with ten people and one heater. We didn't have electric mattresses. The beds were cold. Sometimes, I went shopping but couldn't afford to buy food. I longed for a red bean cake sold on the streets.

I stayed for two months. When it was almost New Year, I called home. My mother said I didn't have to marry that man, so I went home. When I arrived, I realized my mother had lied. My family had prepared everything for the wedding. There were Tibetan robes, coral necklaces, etc. I was to be married on the fifth day of the New Year.

As a rural woman who never attended school, I had to obey my parents before I married. After I married, I had to obey my husband, who is two years older than me and has only a fifth-grade

primary school education. Even when we look for work, we can only find manual labor with dirt and stones.

A woman who has attended school and obtained higher education can take exams for state employment and have the opportunity to work to earn a salary without relying on her husband. I'm like a yak without horns. I regret not getting an education, but I'm no fool. It's just a bad time for women of my generation. My parents didn't think girls needed to attend school. They thought women just needed to marry well.

Every year, I accompany my husband in collecting caterpillar fungus. We can collect caterpillar fungus, but more and more people can now do the same. Herdsmen allow more people to make more money from the land fee. They don't care if we find caterpillar fungus. The high land fee and the hardships of avoiding checkpoints made us do something more adventurous.

One year, we went to Mgo log Prefecture to collect caterpillar fungus, following a group of villagers. Some had been secretly collecting caterpillar fungus for two years. We arrived by van at Dar lag (Dari) County in Mgo log Prefecture. When we reached the base of a mountain, a knowledgeable man informed us that we could cross the mountain to collect caterpillar fungus on the other side illegally. My husband, four other people, and I, each carrying large packs filled with mattresses and food, got out of the truck and started to climb the mountain. The path leading up the mountain was extremely narrow. We walked along the cliff's edge with a large river below us. I proceeded cautiously, carrying a heavy backpack. My husband pushed me when I couldn't climb. Sometimes, I was on my hands and knees. If you weren't careful, you might fall into the river. I heard about a man carrying a heavy bag. He slipped and fell to his death when the sack's rope went around his neck and strangled him.

The river was so loud I couldn't hear other people. Cliffs and forests were on both sides. We made it safely over the big mountain the first night but were blocked by the big river. We were exhausted from walking all day, so we pitched our tents by the river and rested.

The next morning, we saw a few people carrying heavy bags like us, trying to figure out how to cross the river to reach the other

side. A few men sawed down a large tree, positioned it over the river, and put up a rope to hold onto when crossing. I held the rope as I slowly crawled on the log across the river. The river flowed rapidly below. As I approached the other side, a couple following me with too much baggage fell into the rushing water. People quickly noticed, and there was commotion all around. Eventually, they washed into a river valley. Fortunately, everyone worked together to rescue them.

Once on the mountain's opposite side, we noticed it was not frequently patrolled. We peeled bark from the trees, spread it on the ground, and set up our tents. After building mud stoves, we collected wood to make a fire. We collected for two days and learned the police were coming to evict us. During the day, we moved the tents, concealed all the food in a pit covered with pine branches, fled into the woods, and hid. At nightfall, we returned to pitch the tents and sleep.

One night, policemen suddenly appeared. My husband and I hastily hid our tent and luggage, followed an acquaintance into a cave in the dark, and spent the night there. Five of us heard others outside running about, searching for a hiding place. The night was so dark they could not locate one another and shouted their names. I heard a man say that 500 people like us must be in this valley. We hid in the cave and didn't feel safe enough to return to our tent until the next afternoon. We fearfully collected like this every day for a few more days.

Whenever I started to hide, I brought some of my cooked flour, instant noodles, soybeans, and dry buns to eat. I used an empty bottle to catch melted water from the ice in the cave. We took turns drinking, but there wasn't enough water. We couldn't sleep in the caves at night. There wasn't enough space. We had to share with four or five others. It was cold and uncomfortable. When we returned to our tent the next day, the area was full of tents, pots, pans, and food scraps left by people who had decided they couldn't endure it any longer. My husband, the remaining ten couples, and I stayed behind for about fifteen days before moving to another mountain.

One night, we learned that the police were on their way again. My husband told me to grab our bag of caterpillar fungus and

follow a relative who supposedly knew a secure hiding spot. He made it clear that I should follow this person until the end. It was almost dark.

I packed my bags and realized my husband was missing. I took my caterpillar fungus bag and went to look for my relative. Many others in the valley were hiding from the police. When I arrived at my relatives' tent, no one was there. I panicked and looked for people. Luckily, others in the valley were also running around. I asked if anyone had seen my relatives, and after a while, I found them. As I walked close behind five of them, an older relative urged me not to follow them. He lied that others had a good place to hide. The night was dark and scary, and I did not know anyone apart from them. I sensed he didn't want me to follow them. I couldn't figure out who they were following. I ignored him and followed them. Six of us squeezed into a cave where we were hungry, thirsty, and cramped. The inside of the cave was small and full of dirt. Everyone was so cramped that we were nearly kissing each other.

Sitting opposite me was a woman whose husband had recently passed away. As she faced me and inhaled and exhaled, I felt uneasy. We locals think widows have bad luck. When we were next to each other, breathing together, I worried she would aggravate my already bad eyes.

As time passed, one of the older men said there seemed to be no sound outside, went out to check, came back inside the cave, and said that no one was close outside, but added he saw policemen take several people away. I was worried my husband was among those taken away. I begged the widow to accompany me back to the tent to see what was happening, and she agreed.

We went to our tent, where there were some people. When I asked if anyone had seen my husband, someone said, "Your husband is over there talking to someone," which relieved me greatly.

When I met my husband, I asked him where he had gone alone and told him how worried I had been. He didn't seem at all worried about me. We stayed and collected caterpillar fungus for a few more days.

A few days later, everyone was preparing to move to another mountain, so my husband went ahead to occupy a place to pitch our tent. I was left to walk slowly behind with our luggage on my back. It was raining heavily that day. My clothes were soaked, and I couldn't keep up with the others. A woman companion walking with me said, "Let's walk slowly. How can we keep up with those in front of us? They are all crazy," then she wept.

I also sobbed as I walked. After walking for the entire day, my husband was waiting for me with the tent pitched near the river. Since no one could cross the river, we decided to stop and continue our journey the following morning.

The next morning, someone positioned a log across the river, and everyone began slowly crossing it. I observed a man climbing the log in front of me, so I followed him. If someone was in front of me, I wouldn't feel dizzy. I followed him for a bit and then fell into the river. Everyone came to my rescue.

My husband angrily called me stupid for walking after someone else.

When we got to the valley, everybody scrambled for a place to pitch their tents and searched for branches to make a fire. My bag with food and flour fell into the water, so my husband and I had to borrow food from our relatives. After several days of collecting caterpillar fungus, a person kept cautioning the police might intervene, encouraging us to leave. Some said we should leave before something happened. Others said, "We have all persisted until now. We must continue."

It rained for a few days. My feet were so cold I couldn't sleep at night. I put my feet in a plastic bag and wrapped them in my clothes, but they were frostbitten the next day.

Another rainy night. The rain and thunder were very loud and scary. In the middle of the night, we heard a loud bang that I felt was an earthquake. I was terrified and wanted to rush out of the tent. However, my husband held me by the hair and ordered me to take cover inside the tent.

After the rain stopped, my husband checked outside and reported that a mudslide had crashed into the river. We were afraid

to leave the tent and remained indoors for some days. Conditions were so scary we gave up and went home.

In addition to collecting caterpillar fungus, my husband and I do other work outside our village. After I had three children and was about twenty-five, I went with my husband to find my first job.

B couple from our village worked at a construction site in Ziling City and accompanied us to a large construction site with ten buildings. Each had thirty-three floors. Our boss and most of the workers were from Sichuan.

We installed underfloor heating and poured cement over the underfloor heating pipes.

There were a couple of Chinese women in their forties and fifties. We women lived in a dormitory room. Perhaps the boss thought women were of no use. Initially, he assigned us to do some work. After a few weeks, he stopped giving us women any tasks. I couldn't understand the boss's and the other workers' Sichuan accents. He called me an idiot. After twenty days, the boss fired us. He said there were too many people, and he needed to lay off staff. My husband and husband B stayed at the construction site to continue working while I went home with B's wife.

I started harvesting soon after I got home. After forty days of work, my husband returned home to help me. He told me he had informed the Sichuan boss that he had to harvest and rest and intended to return to work after harvest. I was happy to hear that but worried about what I would do without my husband. He assured me that he would beg his boss to hire me. The boss then agreed to let me work there.

Surprisingly, I was the only female worker there except for the boss's wife. The employees were men between forty and in their sixties. B got into an argument with the boss because the boss didn't pay him on time, so he quit and left. As a result, my husband and I were the only Tibetans at the site.

Since female employees had no accommodation, my husband and I slept in a man's dormitory room. The bunks could only accommodate one person. We had to add an extra board and crowd together to sleep. Ten other men in the dorm suggested we buy a curtain and hang it over our bed. They said they were a bit

embarrassed. I slept near a window so the other men couldn't see me.

In the beginning, I hardly talked to these men. My Chinese is poor, and I couldn't understand their Sichuan dialect. Perhaps due to their maturity, they were cautious around me, wearing shirts and pants in the dorm and refraining from walking bare-chested or behaving inappropriately towards me. I was so helpless and bored every day that I thought I would never work there again.

We ate in a big cafeteria with rice, chicken, and cabbage. Many people lined up to get food when at mealtime. We had green (ten RMB) and red (five RMB) meal tickets. We gave the server a ticket and chose the food we wanted. My husband told me to buy food because he knew I was afraid to speak Chinese, and in ten days, I became very proficient at buying food.

Every morning, we woke up at six-twenty a.m., had breakfast in the cafeteria, and then gathered at our workplace for our morning shift. There were no toilet breaks. I finished my work at noon, had lunch, and started the afternoon shift at one-thirty p.m. There was no designated noon break. I finished my shift at seven p.m. The time after that was my own.

In the first month, the team leader assigned me to follow Chinese workers who were responsible for laying rebars on the basement floor. I tied the rebar with thin wire in two layers with hand pliers. For the remaining two months, the workers poured concrete on the basement floor, and I used tools to spread the concrete. That's all I did in those three months.

My husband was responsible for pouring concrete on each building floor, so concrete splattered him every day. Daily contact with Chinese workers familiarized me with them and the working environment. The boss also took good care of us. He praised my husband and me for being hardworking and doing a good job. Every time we ate, he encouraged us to eat a little more. Even though his wife told him to mind his business, he ignored her. It's good when a boss urges you to eat more for dinner.

Occasionally, he scolded us. When a machine broke down and couldn't be repaired for half a day, the boss would especially

scold us for resting on the side and not working. He also scolded us if we worked slowly or didn't do much work.

My husband and I worked from the ninth to the eleventh lunar months, and then we returned home. We could have continued working like the Chinese until the Spring Festival. The boss also advised us to stay on, but we had to go home. My parents-in-law and three children were at home. My husband and I couldn't work away from home for long periods and ignore our family.

After a month of waiting at home, our wages were put on the bank cards. The boss said the company's project department lacked the money to pay us promptly. We didn't push the boss. We wrote a certificate with the boss that served as proof of an outstanding payment, put the bank card numbers on it, signed it, and then returned home. After a month at home, my husband called the boss. We both had worked for three months. My husband earned 160 RMB a day, and I earned 140 RMB a day. Almost 30,000 RMB was then transferred to our bank cards. We then felt this boss was reliable, so we worked with him for four years. Even though he didn't pay the monthly salary on time, my husband and I were sometimes paid 500 or 1,000 RMB a month in advance for living expenses if we lacked money or had an emergency.

In the fifth year, the boss told us that his project in Zi ling was finished and suggested we go to Lanzhou City to continue working. Even though Lanzhou is near Zi ling, this was my first time out of the province. I didn't know Chinese characters, so I stayed close to my husband. We took a train there. We almost got lost when we reached Lanzhou because we took a bus in the wrong direction. Luckily, our new boss was nice, patiently explained how to get to the proper bus, and said he would wait for us at the construction site. He happily greeted us when we arrived, impressing us.

Most Lanzhou laborers had worked in Zi ling, so I was familiar with them and their Sichuan dialect. I was in charge of the cement mixer. After a driver unloaded a truckload of cement bags on the ground, a laborer and I needed to dump each bag into the mixer. I periodically added water during the mixing process to ensure consistency. Sometimes, I needed to sign a receipt when the

driver unloaded the cement bags. I am illiterate, so I had to ask someone to read or sign the receipt each time.

Working in Lanzhou, where the weather was warm, was great compared to working in Zi ling. The boss raised both of our salaries. My husband was paid 250 RMB a day, and I was paid 150 RMB a day. We did not sign a contract with our boss when we worked on the Zi ling site. When we were in Lanzhou, our boss said we had to sign a contract to protect our safety, attend meetings, and have personal safety training about workers' rights and interests.

I was the only woman working at that site. Though I had become familiar with the Sichuan workers, I was lonely and bored. I had no cell phone because I spent most of my time with my husband. I was unfamiliar with Chinese characters, so I did not ask my husband to buy me one.

When I was working in Lanzhou, my husband's grandfather passed away, so my husband had to go home for the funeral, leaving me alone at the construction site. I dared not go anywhere by myself for almost ten days. I stayed alone in the dormitory after work. I stayed alone, slept without a cell phone every day, and avoided chatting with the workers.

My husband and I went home after three months in Lanzhou. We took the boss's car when we returned to Zi ling. While my husband and I were getting ready to join the Sichuan boss the next year, his daughter informed us that he had drowned in his family fishpond and her husband had taken over his work. My husband and I wished to continue working, so we had to follow the new boss's arrangements. He was strict. When he heard that I was illiterate, he said there was no suitable work for me and refused to allow me to accompany my husband to work. I then had no choice but to stay home while my husband continued to work at a Xi'an construction site for a year.

The new boss was very strict, frequently assigned heavy tasks, and gave him little time to rest. He also cursed a lot, further prompting my husband to leave.

I understand my husband because we followed the Sichuan boss for years, had become friends, and he allowed me, a woman, to join my husband in his work. My husband and I were very grateful.

Later, my husband and I resumed job hunting. One year, my husband followed a Chinese boss to work in Yinchuan City, Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region. The boss did not accept illiterate women like me, so I followed a young couple from our village to work in a cement factory in Dga' bde (Gande) County, Mgo log Prefecture. That was a tiring, heavy job compared to what I had done in Zi ling. While working in Zi ling, I was given lighter tasks because I was a woman. However, in my new job, the boss treated me like a male employee, expecting me to carry fifty bags of cement a day. Each bag weighed fifty kilograms. Though the work was the same, women were paid fifty RMB a day less than men. I got about 150 RMB a day. No matter how hard I worked, I did not get compliments from the boss. Without my husband, I was just a single woman there. Some workers said, "It's sad you're working here alone."

The boss intentionally gave me additional tasks since I had no spouse to support and defend me.

The wife of the young couple from our village was the cook. She washed and chopped vegetables before meals for the entire workforce of more than 200 people. She had to rinse the workers' used dishes in cold water for long periods. After a month of work, she was unable to work normally because of menstrual cramps and severe pain in her lower back and abdomen. He agreed when she told the boss she needed a break but deliberately deducted her wages for the five days she had taken off. We female employees asked the boss to consider menstrual cramps as a workplace injury, as frequent exposure to cold water led to illness. He refused. I am thankful my menstrual cramps aren't serious, especially after having three children. I don't feel discomfort when I have my period. I pay attention to my physical well-being and avoid contact with cold water as much as possible.

We worked in poor conditions, lacking comfortable sleeping arrangements and immediate access to hot water. Many women think it is shameful to talk about menstruation. When experiencing

menstrual cramps, you must care for yourself because others may not provide the necessary care.

After working for years, I don't want to go to work with my grumpy husband, who scolds me and loses his temper when I don't obey him. Sometimes, he misunderstood me and suspected there were feelings between me and male workers. We would then quarrel or not speak to each other for days. He would go out with the male co-workers when we were off work or on break but wouldn't tell me beforehand. Even when we went shopping together, and he bought whatever he wanted, he didn't care what I thought, ignoring my feelings and opinions.

On one occasion in Zi ling, our Sichuan bosses arranged for us to sleep alone in the company warehouse in a dark, cold, dimly lit basement. We both slept in a small room with a bed. Every night, we heard mice running around. I was afraid to sleep there without my husband. However, my husband sometimes didn't return after eating, drinking, and playing cards with his male coworkers. I hated that he left me alone, and I cannot forget the nights I was alone, cold, and afraid. I didn't have a cell phone at night. I was desperate, but I had to rely on him. Whenever we quarreled, I would say, "I don't want to go to work with you."

He angrily replied, "You can go to work without me, but you have to make as much money as I do."

He was forcing me to follow him. How could I, an illiterate woman, make as much as a man? I can only speak simple Chinese. When I work outside, I have to follow other people. I wouldn't rely on others if I could read.

In addition to following my husband to collect caterpillar fungus and work, I was also a daughter-in-law married into another family. I had to stay home, do farm work, do housework, and care for my aging parents-in-law. My three children attended the boarding middle school in Bis mdo Town. I work outside most of the year and spend little time with my children, who spend a lot of time with their grandparents and have a better relationship with them than I do.

Working at home is more mentally and physically demanding than working outside. At home, I must cook, wash

dishes, and do farm work daily. Even rainy days are not rest days for me. As a daughter-in-law, you cannot be lazy. Otherwise, your parents-in-law and some outsiders in the village might judge you. Every day at home, I do chores and farm work.

In contrast, going out to work gives me some freedom. As long as I finish my daily tasks, I can relax at the end of the day. At home, I have to deal with my parents-in-law. Outside, I can wear my favorite clothes, use cosmetics, and style my hair.

ACCOUNT Three: Sgrol ma (b. 1983)

I have eight siblings. I am the youngest daughter. My mother has been married twice. Both husbands are deceased. She was fifteen when she first married. After two children, her first husband was tragically killed by a building that collapsed in heavy rain. My mother's family then arranged for her to marry her husband's brother. She had seven children with him.

During the Cultural Revolution (1966-1976), my mother's second husband, my father, worked with a local incarnation *bla ma*, who was tortured and criticized by villagers and passed away. My mother was in her forties when my father died. I was two years old. My mother and grandparents raised all of us. Only one of my brothers could attend a government school, while the rest had to work for the family. Very few children attended school at that time. Most stayed at home to work, especially the girls. Every day after breakfast, my mother sent me to work. We kids just thought about how to have fun. I walked to a stream with a basket on my back, collected cow dung, and put it in the basket while discussing what game to play with my partners. Sometimes, we spent all day by the river playing with *the ge* 'sheep ankle bones' until our hands and clothes were covered with dirt. We reluctantly went home when our mothers came to call us.

Sometimes, I went home, dumped a basket full of cow dung on the ground, and returned to the woods to play shuttlecock with my friends after lunch. After dinner, we ran out of the house and went with friends to a grove by the river, climbed trees to break branches, picked up branches on the ground, and made a bonfire.

When a small group gathered around the campfire, we asked the older ones to tell stories, and we were so engrossed in the stories that we forgot to hurry home. When a storyteller said he would leave, we would grab his leg and not let him go. We promised two candies if he would tell a story.

I saved the candy given by adults on New Year's Eve to give to storytellers. Looking back, I was addicted to playing, doing few chores, and running out to play until dark. My mother would yell at me to come home. If I came home late, I would be beaten.

Childhood went by without a care. At sixteen, I started working with a shovel first. Thinking about the family's poor economic conditions, I went to Xunhua County Town with a cousin to look for work. A Salar boss introduced us to work in a Salar village for fifteen RMB a day. My main task was shoveling sand full of gravel into a truck. I couldn't lift the shovel properly because I was scrawny. Lacking the strength to shovel efficiently, I put the shovel against my thighs, and after a while, red and painful deep marks appeared from the pressure. My fingers were calloused and swollen. I feared the Salar boss would say I did not work well, so I endured the pain every day.

Everyone worked hard, so I dared not rest. We lived in a temporary tent set up by the owner. Most meals were fried potatoes and vegetables, fried cabbage, and steamed buns. Even if there was no meat, I thought it was delicious.

I don't remember how long I stayed and how much money I made, but I remember giving all the money to my mother. I was happy to earn money for my family.

At seventeen, I went to Sog rdzong (Henan) Mongolian Autonomous County to collect caterpillar fungus with relatives of my family. Then I went to Them chen (Tianjun) County to work building houses. Chinese workers were contracted to build the houses. I assisted three of them in supplying mortar, cement, and bricks. The workers were experienced and did everything quickly and skillfully. I handed a bucket of mortar to a worker, and by the time I returned with bricks, the bucket was empty. The bricks were finished when I got some bricks after giving another bucket of mortar. I could quickly hand the bricks to the workers when they were next to me.

When the nearby bricks were used up, I had to carry more from a distance, which was a time-consuming task.

Sometimes, the work was exhausting. Even though a single brick wasn't very heavy, repeatedly carrying and passing them all day drained me, but I had to keep going without a break. The hardest part was that I didn't speak Chinese at the time. During the day, I was sent to different places to work. I had to rely on gestures and repetition to understand the workers' orders. I quickly learned to recognize when they asked for mortar or other materials and memorized the names of items through constant use. Every time I listened to the workers, I was very nervous and careful, fearing that I would make a mistake and be scolded. It was hard to communicate when I didn't speak Chinese well. I was bored until I got off work.

The work was heavy, and I was exhausted every day. I especially missed my mother. I wasn't in the mood when others wore nice clothes and went shopping. I don't know why. I just wore my mother's clothes and missed her.

I was eighteen when I went to Brag dkar (Xinghai) County to dig for gold in a canyon. There were also Chinese workers in the canyon who were extracting stones. I heard the Chinese had worked there for over ten years without going home. They blew up the mountains and put rocks from the explosions into a big truck. I was responsible for picking up white stones with gold and carrying them to a big truck for the driver to transport. When we put gravel in water, we saw gold appear.

I went there to work with fellow villagers - five or six girls and two boys. The five girls slept on our mattresses in a white canvas tent while the two boys shared another tent with the Chinese workers. A day's pay was thirty RMB. The conditions were harsh. We ate plain noodles every day. It was very cold at night in the ninth lunar month. Still, I was happy at that time. The girls had endless conversations every day. The boys would chat with us and tell ghost stories to scare us. Some girls and boys flirted.

Limited water and no toilets were difficulties. The boss brought drinking water from outside in buckets. We rarely had enough water to wash our clothes and hair. The boss was very strict

and didn't allow us to leave the tent freely when we weren't working. We couldn't leave the work site for almost two months. Everyone went to a ravine to go to the toilet. This made the girls uncomfortable when we encountered men going to the toilet. Going to the toilet was troublesome for me.

I heard some Chinese workers were killed in cave explosions, while others were crushed by falling rocks. We did odd jobs. Some of us were only eighteen. Many Tibetans were working there at the time; otherwise, the Chinese workers might have bullied us. After working for two months, we went home. On the way back, several girls bought fashionable suits of clothes, and we felt very beautiful.

I married my current husband when I was twenty-six. He and I met through friends. After getting to know each other for a while, he called me on my landline one day and asked me to meet him. I stayed with him. When my family learned this, they were very angry. My parents didn't approve of me marrying him. They thought I had disobeyed them and humiliated them by sneaking off.

I don't regret what I did because my family arranged my marriage to my ex-husband, whom I didn't even know at the time. My eldest brother was the one who forced me to marry. He told me he would kick me out of the house if I refused to marry who they had chosen for me. I could only obey.

I was nineteen when I married my ex-husband, a businessman specializing in buying and selling caterpillar fungus. He lived with his father. His mother had passed away when he was a child. Their family condition was good. I was pregnant a year later. I still wanted to earn money by collecting caterpillar fungus, so I decided to go collect, and my husband agreed. I worked as a hired laborer with my relatives to collect caterpillar fungus in Rma stod (Maduo) County, Mgo log Prefecture, and earned 6,000 RMB a month.

I was skinny, so the boss who hired me didn't realize I was pregnant. However, I'm one of those who isn't very good at collecting caterpillar fungus. I was frustrated and ashamed when others collected more caterpillar fungus than me. The mountains in that area are very high. Others climbed those mountains daily to collect

caterpillar fungus. At first, I could keep up with them, but later, I realized I didn't have enough strength. Those who didn't know I was pregnant laughed at me and called me lazy. After finishing work, everyone returned to their tents, where we socialized and enjoyed each other's company. The boss rewarded the most efficient collectors. We sang, danced, and ate snacks together.

My belly was hard as a rock for several nights and was so painful I couldn't move or eat. All I wanted was to lie down and sleep. Luckily, some relatives knew I was pregnant and took care of me. I lasted a month and then went home. I gave all the money I had earned to my husband. I helped my father-in-law harvest the crops and gave birth to a daughter in winter.

My husband often didn't come home. I don't know what I did wrong. Maybe he changed. The next year, he became increasingly cold. Our relationship worsened. One day, I angrily returned to my natal home and we officially separated two years later. Since then, we have each lived our own lives. My family members encouraged us to reconcile, but I learned my ex-husband was not willing to reconcile. I was extremely disappointed in him.

His family took care of my daughter after we divorced. I thought about my daughter every day and vividly dreamed of her. My family noticed this. I stayed home and did nothing while constantly worrying about my child. They then persuaded me to go outside the village to work to take my mind off things. I thought it might help me see things more openly, so I went to work building a bridge in Chu dmar leb (Qumalai) County, Yul shul (Yushu) Prefecture with my cousin. That job eased some of my pain. Gradually, I rarely thought about my daughter because I was busy working every day.

My cousin and I went with some men from the village. We were paid one hundred RMB a day. At first, the Salar boss arranged for my cousin and me to cook for fifteen workers. Although cooking is not that difficult, I didn't want to do it. A woman from our village really wanted to cook, but the boss wouldn't let her. After my cousin and I worked as cooks for a month, it was time for the Salar's fast, and the Salar boss wouldn't let the two of us cook because they had

to get up at four a.m. to eat. So, he got a couple of Salar women to do the cooking.

That Salar boss was particularly good. He urged us to eat more every day and to rest at noon. He was concerned about our well-being and mentioned that our family would worry if we became thin. We switched jobs from cooks to laborers. We followed the workers daily, assisting them in carrying items and handing them bricks and cement. I came home after two months in Chu dmar leb County. My family members said my physical and mental states had improved. As long as I was in a good mood, it didn't matter how much work I did, but if my heart was in pain, it was painful to do easy work. Shortly after I came home, my ex-husband's family told our family, "You can have your daughter if you want to raise her. If you don't, we'll give her to someone else to raise."

I was angry when I heard this! Why would they give their child to someone else to raise? If they didn't want to raise her, why did they take her away from me in the first place? I would raise my own child even if I were poor. I would rather raise her than someone else, so I took my daughter.

After living in my natal home for less than two years, I lived with my present husband, a former monk who was five years my senior. I followed him to work every year. One of my eyes had a sarcoma, and my husband wasn't much of a collector of caterpillar fungus. We didn't collect caterpillar fungus. He was very kind to me when we first met. When he learned I had a daughter in my natal home, he arranged to bring her to our home to raise.

I felt he was not treating me well after I gave birth to two more daughters. I know girls can't compete with boys no matter how hard they try, especially when it comes to important things, because girls are useless. For instance, in case one of her parents passes away, daughters might appear fragile and show their grief by crying, while boys might endure the pain silently. Especially when a corpse needs to be cremated, a man carries it to the cremation place. Women lack the courage to do it.

My husband and his family didn't force me to have a son. They thought that it was their fate. In a dream, I was walking in a forest. After I saw a particularly straight tree in the distance, I ran to

it and found that it was crooked. So, I switched to a different tree, but it was also crooked. I couldn't find a straight tree as I ran around. I gave birth to a daughter the next day.

When I started working with my husband in Yul shul County, he was very nice, and I didn't have to worry about anything. He bought my tickets, carried my luggage, and purchased various delicious snacks for me. We were there with three couples from the same village. It was just a year after the earthquake.¹ The main street in Yul shul County was full of houses that had begun to be rebuilt. Our job was to rebuild Skye dgu mdo (Jiegu) Monastery. The daily wage was 130 RMB for my husband and one hundred RMB for me. I was responsible for shoveling dirt into a handcart and transporting it back and forth every day.

Everyone slept together in a single disaster relief tent, as this job was part of a government project for post-disaster reconstruction. We ate and drank well every day, with meat at every meal. At that time, the boss and most workers were Chinese, so we needed to communicate in Chinese daily. My Chinese wasn't good. Whenever the boss assigned me work, I nodded and said, "Okay," and did the work diligently and conscientiously so he would like me.

My husband's Chinese is not good, but he has a lot of confidence and would argue with the boss. There were several days when I wanted to leave work at seven p.m., but the boss would suddenly assign me more tasks. I didn't dare refuse and ended up working until after ten p.m. When my husband found out, he scolded me for being stupid. He ran to the boss and asked why a woman had been sent to work overtime without being paid. The boss was also angry and felt my husband was provoking him. Luckily, some workers talked them down that day, or they would have fought for sure. After this incident, I felt that the boss didn't like us and looked at us coldly. We worked for two months and went home.

My husband changed after I had given birth to our two daughters. Once, when we went out to work together, I was dizzy and vomited because of the bus. I was feeble. My husband was very

¹ On 14 April 2010, six earthquakes struck Yul shul County with a maximum magnitude of 7.1 at 7:49 a.m.

impatient and ignored me. We were ready to carry our luggage when we reached the Zi ling bus station. Loaded with mats and quilts, we looked for a hotel. I thought my husband would help me carry what we had, but he randomly picked up a light bag and left, not waiting for me or helping me carry the heavier bags. I was afraid of losing him, so I tried my best to follow him, but he walked faster and faster.

I was soon too tired to keep up with him and sadly wondered, "Why doesn't he care about me?"

Thinking about this, I angrily put my luggage on the side of the road, squatted in the middle of a crowd, and wept. I really thought I'd lost my husband. I didn't know what to do. As I was sitting there in great despair, my idiot husband returned and asked, "What's wrong with you? Are you not feeling well?"

I replied, "Didn't you see me vomiting on the bus? I'm the one carrying the quilt. Why don't you carry it?"

He said nothing and helped me carry the bags. We looked for a hotel and stayed in one near the bus station for one night. When we left the next day, I had to carry luggage on my back with great difficulty. A waitress looked at my husband and said, "This is your wife, and you are not carrying this stuff. Aren't you ashamed!"

When my husband heard this and saw Chinese women looking at him, he was embarrassed and helped me carry the bags.

Worse, he began to beat and scold me. Several times we quarreled over something during work. When he was outraged, he would take me to a place where no one could see and beat me. My heart was very painful, and I did not want to stay with him, but thinking of my three daughters, I could only bear it.

One of my most painful job experiences was when I was three or four months pregnant with my youngest daughter. My husband took me to a town neighboring Chen gangs rgyal (Kekexili) in Yushu Prefecture. I forgot the exact location. The work was easy, involving filling road potholes and cracks, and placing rocks and dirt in pits and crevices.

That place is at an elevation of 4,000 to 5,000 meters. We slept in makeshift tents and couldn't sleep well at night because it was so cold. I felt I was running out of oxygen, and sometimes I couldn't catch my breath. Four or five Chinese workers occasionally

came but only stayed for one or two days. They couldn't bear the high altitude. My husband and I stayed because the boss paid us each 150 RMB a day. After working there for half a month, my health started deteriorating. I wanted to vomit and had acid reflux every time I ate. Periodically, I vomited yellow fluid. My mouth was bitter and astringent, and I couldn't eat, but I still had to work every day like a normal worker. My boss and fellow workers didn't know I was pregnant. A female worker asked, "Are you feeling unwell? Perhaps you should go to the hospital."

It was so challenging that I wanted to cry. However, I didn't dare to say I was pregnant. My husband and I were afraid my boss would fire me. Luckily, when I was working, my boss didn't supervise me all the time, so I had some time and opportunity to rest. My husband and I stayed there for two months and then went home. When I gave birth to my daughter, the doctor told me that my daughter's heart hadn't grown properly and she might have heart problems in the future.

My youngest daughter was particularly prone to illness after she was born. My husband and I took her to the hospital many times and bought a lot of medicine. We didn't have enough money, so we didn't think of an operation. We thought she wouldn't have serious problems. It wasn't until she was five years old and attending a village kindergarten that the doctor said she had a congenital heart disease. This was when the government sent doctors to village kindergartens for medical checkups. The teacher phoned my husband and convinced us to let our daughter have free heart surgery. We agreed. It was when my husband and I worked in Them chen (Tianjun) County. The job was to plant grass in the desert. Each of them was paid one hundred RMB a day. We had been working for two months when we got the call. We both then rushed home. The surgery was successful.

Whenever I earned money, I gave it to my husband. I didn't know how much money we both had. I just asked him for a little bit when I needed money. My husband doesn't give me details about money. If we run out of money, he finds a way to borrow some, and I don't have to worry about it. I was responsible for household chores, serving my in-laws, caring for the children, and performing farm

work. I feel ignorant sometimes, living a life without knowing anything and doing nothing but working every day. My husband thinks I have no burdens and says, "If you want to be the head of the family, you take care of the money in the future."

When he said that, I wimped out again because I was timid and worried about not having enough money. I can't afford to buy clothes for myself, let alone makeup.

Recently, my husband and I spent 150,000 RMB to purchase thirty cow-yak crosses with a loan from the township government and with our savings. Before this, my husband and I left our three children in the care of my parents-in-law, but they are now eighty, and it was an added burden for them.

As a result, my husband and I separated from my in-laws' home and now live in a newly built one-room house, leaving my parents-in-law in the care of my husband's brother. We lived independently, looking after our three children and herding cattle.

In winter and spring, I only have to drive the cows up a hill every day and let them go where they please. I then drive them home before sunset, water them, and feed them grass. In summer and fall, when everyone started planting crops, I needed to herd the cows daily on the mountains during the day to prevent them from going into others' wheat fields.

Compared to women who live with their in-laws, I've been happy with my life after separating from them. I was judged on everything I did when I lived with my in-laws. For example, every time I scooped up noodles, I was afraid that my mother-in-law would say that I had put little meat in her bowl and had put much in my bowl. If I wore a lovely dress, my mother-in-law would say, "You are a mother of three. You can't dress like this."

I washed my panties in the cowshed. I was too shy to let my in-laws see them. My mother-in-law objected to me going shopping with village women. She believed a daughter-in-law should focus on home chores. My husband and I worked outside the home for two or three months a year before we returned home to help harvest the crops. If we didn't, they got angry. I had to consider all of this carefully.

In the past two years, agricultural labor has become more mechanized. Women traditionally handled plowing, fertilizing, and harvesting, while men did less fieldwork. Since most women don't know how to operate the machines, men must take on more responsibilities. My husband now does more agricultural work, which has lessened my fieldwork. His family didn't provide us with financial assistance. We earned everything with our sweat.

I am relieved I don't have to live with my in-laws. Now, I can eat, work, and take breaks whenever I please. If we go out for a hot pot or a good meal, I forget all the pain and feel happy again. If you keep pain in your heart and can't let it go, you can't live.

ACCOUNT Four: Bde skyid (b. 1970)

I mainly worked at home doing housework, farm work, and caring for my in-laws and three children until I was thirty. Only a few men at that time went outside the village to work. Most women stayed at home. I collected cow-yak cross dung and twigs every day after breakfast, which were the most important things for us in our daily lives. Especially in winter, my daily task as a daughter-in-law was to go to the forest and cut wood.

The snow was knee-deep, and my shoes and clothes were covered with snow as I climbed the mountains. As I was just about to climb a tree one day to break off a few branches, I saw the forest keeper coming up a hill in the distance. I was so scared that I left my mule and fled. The forest guard saw me running and shouted, "If you run, I'll find you and cripple your legs!"

He took his rifle and pointed it at me. I said in terror, "Please, don't shoot me! I'm not going to run away," while running down the hill as fast as I could.

Fortunately, the forest guard didn't catch me that day or I'd have been punished. Once I felt the forest keeper was not behind me, I let out a breath. I realized I had been so nervous when I ran that my legs were numb.

Sometimes after supper, I would go to the forest, cut down a tree, and sneak back to the house with the trunk on my back. Some trunks were used to build our house, while others were sold

to Salar. My husband and I even stole trees on New Year's Eve night because there were no forest guards, so we weren't afraid of being caught. We had to pay a fine if we were caught, and the wood would be confiscated.

My mother-in-law complained she was cold when she was sick and in bed, so I had to collect branches even though I was pregnant with my almost-born daughter.

Early one morning, I rode a mule into the mountains to collect branches. I tied them into three bundles, loaded them onto the mule, and carried each bundle home separately. I had a large belly because I was pregnant and had to struggle to lift the bundles onto the mule's back. Lacking strength, I was unable to tie the branches tightly to the mule's back, so the branches kept falling off along the way.

I fell after I put the branches on the mule's back on the third trip home. I was very afraid that my unborn baby had died. My belly became hard, and she didn't move. It was dark when I got home.

I gave birth to my daughter three days later. Fortunately, she was okay. Fifteen days later, I was collecting twigs and cattle-yak dung again.

Women do most of the farm work, and men help sometimes. Women cut the wheat. Men carry the sheaves to the house. If a man comes to cut the wheat, villagers tease him. Our family's crop had six people's share. We continued to cut at night if we couldn't finish cutting during the day. My husband used to accompany me in the evenings to see if the field keepers had come to check our work. The field keepers only allowed us to harvest wheat when it was ripe. If our family were the only one who had not finished cutting wheat, the other families would let their cattle loose. Fearing they might eat our crops, I came at night with a head lamp, cut as much as possible until it was almost dawn and then I went home.

When putting wheat on a donkey, my hands were calloused and blistered. One night, my husband fell asleep while on watch. The field guard then found me and fined me twenty kilograms of wheat.

I was busy every day and still had to cook. Even if you worked very hard, your mother-in-law and husband might have treated you poorly.

It's much better now. With money you can buy cow dung, coal, and electricity. Moreover, women now have freedom to choose their partners, unlike when matchmaking was the norm. I got married at twenty-three in an arranged marriage that was considered late. This was because I needed to assist my parents with their work. Boys were left to study or became monks. Many girls could not marry. Some villagers teased that there were as many unmarried girls as cows.

It wasn't until after my oldest daughter married and my remaining two children went to the boarding high school in Bis mdo Town that I followed my husband to work in my late thirties. We first went to Mdo la (Qilian) County in Mtsho byang (Haibei) Prefecture. Our workplace was near Mtsho sngon po (Qinghaihu, Qinghai Lake), where the temperature was low in the mornings and evenings. My husband was involved in road construction - mixing cement with water, lifting sand with a shovel, and sifting sand. I worked as a cook. Each of us received thirty RMB a day. The Salar boss supervised seven groups. Each group had thirty workers, including Tibetans, Han, and Salar.

Three female cooks were responsible for preparing meals for thirty people each day. We had to wake up at six a.m. to start an electricity generator we used to make bread buns, stir-fry vegetables, and boil water. After preparing breakfast, I cut and cooked vegetables for lunch. Noodles were made for dinner, and buns for the next morning.

Sometimes, we were so busy we had no time to eat. With no electricity at night, I had to boil water over a wood fire for the workers. The boss frequently told us to use less oil to save money when preparing food. However, the workers considered the food flavorless and insisted we add more oil, which made preparing food challenging.

Since all of us workers were recruited by a *nashi* 'middleman who finds workers' before working under the bosses, the bosses didn't know much about us. Several female workers

were pregnant, including one from Bis mdo Town. One day, she was carrying bags of cement, suddenly felt weak, and gave birth. She had been working while pregnant for over a month. The premature infant died within a few days. Her husband buried it.

When the boss found out, he allowed her to rest for seven days but didn't take her to the hospital. To prevent this from happening again, the boss fired the few remaining pregnant women. After this incident, I asked the woman, "Have you recovered? Can you still work?"

She replied, "I'm fine, I can still work."

We worked together for three months and went home in the eleventh lunar month.

My most difficult time was working in Mdzo rgan ra bar (Huashixia) Town, Rma stod (Maduo) County, Mgo log Prefecture. After harvest, my mother's family introduced my husband and me to a Sichuan boss who went there to build herders' houses. I was an assistant laborer serving four workers with a salary of eighty RMB a day. My job involved mixing concrete and handing the workers bricks. It sounds easy, but it's not when you do it. I had to make twenty trips carrying fifty-kilogram cement bags and at least thirty trips carrying mixed cement, mortar, and other materials. My hands were covered with blisters and calluses. Workers were paid by the number of bricks they laid, so they worked fast. Laying a brick took five seconds, and the workers placed 3,000 to 4,000 bricks daily. I couldn't keep up with their pace, so they yelled at me. I couldn't understand their Chinese very well when they scolded me loudly. One worker scolded, "*Mum mu*," 'cow' because I didn't understand Chinese.

The worker was once late for work. Then the boss asked why he was late. He said, "Because the assistant didn't want to work. She was late."

I said, "He's lying. He didn't come on time. I came earlier."

The boss believed me and scolded the worker. Consequently, that worker bullied me by arranging for me to do a lot of work. He threw stones and sand at me when I didn't listen to him. I was so angry that I scolded him in Tibetan and threw stones and

sand back at him. He couldn't understand what I was saying and laughed at me.

After completing one herder's house, we moved to the next one. We had to demolish an old house and move the damaged bricks. I'm always afraid of being struck by bricks while demolishing a house. We lived in tents most of the time. There was no running water or cooking, so we brought water from a river.

Additionally, we stayed far from town. It wasn't easy to buy food, so we asked local herders to give us bread. Some workers secretly stole bread from them.

The daily work was tiring. A female worker worked so hard that her nose ran. She didn't have time to clean it. Snot flowed until it reached her mouth. Everyone laughed at her. Another time, a few of us women went to demolish a house, and dust scattered everywhere. I could not see where my companions were for a moment. I looked into the dust and asked, "Where are you?"

My companions laughed and replied, "Right next to you. Can't you see us?"

We laughed for a long time.

One night the boss and some of his workers fought with locals when they went to town for drinks and dinner. Local herders angrily came to our construction site the next day, saying, "Prepare your weapons. We'll prepare ours. Let's see who wins the fight!"

All the men on the construction site took shovels and sticks and went to fight. We women didn't dare go and talked them out of it, fearing that they would kill someone in the fight. We called the local Public Security Bureau, and police came to stop them.

We finished building a house in about ten days, packed up our bedding, and moved to the next herder's house. The herdsmen were scattered, so we suffered a lot carrying our luggage and building tools to the next house. Some slopes were too steep for a tractor or a truck to cross, so we had to carry our belongings up the slope.

It was still winter. We couldn't build a fire in our makeshift tent at night, so we just put a mat on the cold grass and slept that way. The following day, we woke up to find our tent and covers covered with melting frost.

Sometimes, we were chased by packs of wild dogs. We were also informed that a brown bear had recently attacked a family, which made it difficult for us to sleep at night because we were afraid bears might attack.

Each winter day felt especially cold. Working hard made my body warm, and I was determined to be productive. When I saw male workers slacking off and not working while the boss was away, I scolded, "We women are working hard, but you men just pretend to work when the boss is around. Aren't you ashamed? You've come here to work, and the boss has paid you. Please have a conscience."

The male workers scolded me for being nosy. After three months, my husband and I earned more than 7,000 RMB each and went home happily.

The furthest I've been from my home is Bsang chu (Xiahe) County, Gannan Tibetan Prefecture, where my husband and I worked constructing a river embankment for two months. We were paid one hundred RMB a day each. As an assistant, I carried and handed workers rocks, concrete, and sand. When a driver delivered a truckload of stones, assistant workers loaded them onto tricycle carts, transported them to the worksite, and neatly placed them on the ground. The workers then used the stones to build the embankment. It was summer and rainy. We had to work in the rain, fearing the river would rise and flood. We wore raincoats and rain shoes that the boss bought. We desperately built a pile of rocks by the river; fearing being washed away.

Some construction project leaders watched from inside a car. They said we should take a break from the rain, but we dared not without the boss's order. Without a loader to load and transport the rocks, carrying rocks ourselves was slow and dangerous. Once, I was carrying a rock. It fell and hit my foot. I was off work for a couple of days. We stayed in makeshift tents where men and women slept crammed together. Some people snored and farted when we were in bed at night, making me very uncomfortable.

After two months of work, my husband and I, and seven or eight Chinese workers, planned to quit and go home to harvest, but we couldn't find the boss at the construction site. He didn't answer his phone when we called him. We had no choice but to wait for

about ten days without working. We hadn't signed a contract. Work was based on verbal agreement. We had little money to buy food, so we ate moldy steamed buns and rice every day to survive. I was concerned my husband and I wouldn't have enough money to buy a ticket home. Ultimately, the Chinese workers reported the boss to the local government, which helped us get our wages. Otherwise, we would have worked for nothing.

My husband and I struggled to find work opportunities during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2021. We had to scan our itinerary codes and register our health codes in Chinese using our phones whenever we went out. Neither of us had gone to school beyond the elementary level, so it was challenging to operate more complex setups. As a result, we couldn't look for work far from home and settled for nearby jobs.

A Salar boss came to our village the year after the outbreak and recruited ten women and fifty other villagers. All were women in their fifties. There were no men. The Salar boss told us the job was to grow vegetables and plant the fields. I was worried my husband wouldn't be able to find a job, so I begged the Salar boss to arrange a job for him. Thankfully, he was very nice and arranged for my husband to help his family with goats. The boss's home was in a Salar village next to the highway in Dp'a lung (Hualong) Hui Autonomous County. He had undertaken a government vegetable planting project. Half of the village land and related water resources were his. Villagers who needed to use water resources in the area had to obtain the Salar boss's consent.

My husband herded goats for the boss's family. My husband and I stayed in a house near the boss's home while the other women were transported back and forth by the Salar boss in a truck every day. My job was to plant corn and yams in the fields, construct plastic greenhouses over the crops, and fertilize, water, and spray pesticides on the crops. The boss's wife was kind and asked me to eat at their house every morning. While we women were working, she brought us food and drink. The owner often recruited Tibetan workers. The family spoke Tibetan, which we spoke in daily communication.

The most challenging aspect of working there was the weather. It was hot and dry in the fifth and sixth lunar months. Every day, we worked bent over and covered in sweat. The heat made us uncomfortable. The boss's wife was there to supervise us, so it was hard to have an opportunity to slack off. There were no trees, leaving us with no shade. The nearest shady places were far away by a river. We worked from seven to seven or eight in the evening. We did have a lunch break. We were constantly pushed to work and weren't allowed to chat or talk during work. We were warned not to take too long to go to the toilet. We were exhausted at the end of a day's work.

My husband herded goats for the Salar boss. There were 300 goats at first. After my husband herded them for three months, the Salar boss bought 500 more from a Tibetan herder, adding up to 800 goats. The boss said he'd give my husband and me 5,500 RMB a month each to keep herding goats for him, but we both thought this was too hard. There was no water available in the mountains. We needed to transport the goats to a distant river once in two days before bringing them back to the mountains. This was a challenging task. When my husband and I returned home, my husband got a call from the police station. A policeman asked, "Were you a goat herder? More than 200 goats disappeared. Did you have anything to do with this?"

My husband said, "We counted the goats before leaving. I don't know what happened."

Later, we learned rain and flooding washed over 200 goats into a nearby reservoir. The Salar boss thought the goats had been stolen and suspected my husband. We didn't stay there to avoid my husband getting into trouble.

After more than three months of work for the Salar boss, I was paid 130 RMB and my husband 150 RMB a day, which added up to 25,000 RMB. Our new house had cracks in the walls, so we used the money to repair the damage and improve the house's condition. My husband's brothers divided the family's fields after the deaths of my parents-in-law. We received a small field of three *mu*.

We put herbicides on our crops, so there is little grass to remove. After irrigation, nothing is particularly labor-intensive. We need to farm and don't dare let the fields lie fallow because the government confiscates such land. When my husband and I went out to work, I asked my husband's sister to help farm.

My son and daughter have also started to go out to work. My son worked in an electronics factory in Shanghai for a year after he graduated from vocational school. My daughter also graduated from vocational school last year. She didn't get a job, so she followed her brother to the Shanghai factory. My son went with fifteen young men from our town. They found an agent. If they were paid 160 RMB a day for their work, the agent took forty RMB. But this time, they didn't have to pay the agent when they got there.

These young people were all around twenty-five. They don't want to do farm work at home and can't get a government job when they take an exam, so factory work suits them. If I could speak Chinese, I would like to go there too. My daughter has called me these days and said the factory work was hard. She needs to stand and twist screws in the machines every day. The weather is hot, and she's not accustomed to eating rice. If they stay for two or three years, they can become a team leader and get paid more.

Since we can make money, our family is living a much better life. Before, we ate bread with spices at noon and sugar only during the New Year period. We can now buy various vegetables and fruits at any time. I fill school bags with bread every day when I send my children to primary school. When plastic bags are unavailable, I instruct them to bring them back, or there won't even be enough plastic bags at home. Now, there are so many, I don't even know where to put them.

My hands and feet now have problems after working for many years. I helped a monk relative build a house at Bla brang Monastery in Xiahe County. I washed my hands and feet in the local river. My hands and feet have been sore since then. It's because of the water deities. My son and daughter have persuaded me to rest at home, but I'm not used to staying at home and doing nothing. All the village women think it's better to go out and earn money than

stay home. If you stay home, villagers ask, "Why are you staying home when you are so healthy? Why don't you go out and work?"

In our community, you leave and look for work even if you're fifty or sixty and your hair is gray. People outside say, "Old Auntie, don't you have any children? Why are you still working when you are old?"

They don't understand why we want to work. We're used to working. In our community, we look for work even if we're fifty. This is the life of women around here. We worked for the family when we were children, worked for our husbands' families when we were young, and went out to work when we were middle-aged. We were born to work. The township authorities have been actively seeking street sweepers for the past two days. I'm willing to go. Some villagers say it's embarrassing, but as long as I can earn money, there's nothing to be ashamed of, and the job is very easy, just sweeping and taking garbage from the streets.

Speaking of here, women in herding areas have grassy hills, yaks, sheep, and caterpillar fungus. Most of them don't go to work. We used to have yaks and sheep. When we returned from collecting caterpillar fungus, we stayed home to look after the livestock. My in-laws were a bit younger and could help at home, but once they were old, they couldn't care for them, so we had to sell all the livestock.

Salar women are quite relaxed, running restaurants or selling clothes, and dressing up daily, unlike us, who are grey and grimy. When we work, Salar men said, "Others will laugh at wives of our Salar men if they do heavy and dirty work outside. Tibetan women are pitiful, doing dirty, heavy work."

That makes sense. We suffer so much because those male migrant laborers are not capable of making money. I chatted with farmer women in Gcan tsha (Jianzha) and Dp'a lung counties. They were just like us and worked outside their homes. Those with little land only went home during the New Year. Few women work in restaurants. Most villagers say that it's only a place for young women. If you work with a shovel, you get paid more and get home whenever you need to go, so we chose this job. The village atmosphere has been bad for a few years now. Everyone competes.

I want to earn more than you. If your family built a new house, I want to build one. Everyone is very busy making money.

My husband and I collected caterpillar fungus when we were young. Once a year in the fourth lunar month, my husband and I carried twenty-five kilograms of bags of flour on our backs, along with mats and quilts, and slept on the grasslands, facing the stars in fear wild dogs would attack us. Sometimes we couldn't find a car and climbed mountains with our heavy luggage. After paying the land fee with the money saved from hard work, we went home with caterpillar fungus. It was difficult to sell the caterpillar fungus for a good price.

We have to go out to work to earn money and work for one or two months. I look for a boss to work in the sixth and seventh lunar months after harvesting our wheat, plowing, drying the wheat grain in the sun, and sacking it. Whenever I go to a new place, I am nervous about getting up early, what I will do, who I will go with, who I will be around, how much I will be paid, and the food. It took about five days to get used to it. Then it was time to move and hand bricks, make concrete, and operate mixers. We worked until winter, when pigs were slaughtered. If there was no other place to work, we went home. After the pigs were slaughtered, cooked, and eaten between the tenth and the fifteenth of the tenth lunar month, we started preparing for the New Year by working on religious activities in the village.

I was a daughter-in-law who faced parents-in-law every day, cared for children, did endless farm and housework, and dealt with my in-laws' bad treatment and my husband's beating. Divorce is shameful. For the sake of your natal family's reputation and your children, you can't divorce. When I was younger, my husband beat me at home, and once when I was working outside because I was talking with men at the construction site. My husband was jealous and beat me. Fortunately, some people persuaded him to stop. Now that I'm older and without my in-laws, I've made my husband's home my own, so I must worry about everything in this house.

ACCOUNT Five: Me tog (b. 1969)

I don't know what I did in my last life, but I was destined to be miserable after I married. I'm here to redeem myself in this life. I've never done anything bad to anyone. Even if I can't help them, I've never harmed them. I was an only daughter. My parents arranged for me to marry a man from another village when I was nineteen. I had three girls in a row. I had to have a fourth to have a son. The birth control policy was very strict at that time. Government people came to my house every day to force me to have a birth control ring to prevent me from having another child. My family gave my third daughter to a relative in a neighboring village so that I could have a fourth child. She lives with that relative and doesn't come to my home.

When I gave birth to my son and thought I could live happily, my husband was diagnosed with Hepatitis B. Our family spent a lot of money on his treatment. I can't imagine how I would have survived without my parents' help. My parents are farmers. Their only income is from farming. They help me care for my husband and children. I go out alone every year to work.

I collect caterpillar fungus to earn a lot of money quickly. Every spring, I first planted crops at home. After weeding a few times, I carried sheets and food on my back and followed my relatives from neighboring villages to collect caterpillar fungus. The landowner will allow you to collect if you pay rent for the land. Collecting until the caterpillar fungus harvesting season ends is up to you. Many women feel that collecting caterpillar fungus is very hard. I disagree. When the caterpillar fungus is newly exposed, it is fresh and small. If you look carefully, you will find it.

The year after I gave birth to my son, at the age of twenty-seven, I went to the Rgan gya (Ganjia) grasslands in Gannan Prefecture to collect caterpillar fungus. I followed my relatives from the neighboring village. I paid 300 RMB and collected for a month. I wasn't very experienced, so I didn't find many. One earned five RMB, and I collected about 1,500.

I didn't give up. I had to find more when I thought about raising three kids at home and taking care of my sick husband. The

best year was when I went to Mgo log Prefecture with my oldest daughter in 2010. Only a herding couple and a man were on that mountain land that year. I paid 3,000 RMB for my daughter and my collection fee. We collected many. The herding couple kindly sent us to the bus station after a month on the day we were to leave. My daughter and I were on the evening bus. I was holding our caterpillar fungus bag. My daughter slept after we boarded the bus. I worried that the bag would be stolen and didn't dare sleep. When we arrived in Zi ling the next morning, we got off the bus and called my husband, who was consulting a doctor, to come and pick us up. I didn't breathe a sigh of relief until I saw my husband. Caterpillar fungus sold for twenty RMB per piece on average, and we made 40,000 RMB after we sold them all.

Whenever I see healthy husbands bringing their wives along to collect caterpillar fungus, I envy them. My husband suffered from a serious illness. The doctor said he would not be able to do heavy work and would have to be treated with injections, medication, and surgery to be completely cured. No matter how hard it is to collect caterpillar fungus, I go around every year borrowing money from my relatives and friends to get the money for the land payment to collect caterpillar fungus. I don't want my husband to die at a young age. I want my three children to have a father. I even took my oldest daughter in the third grade to collect with me.

My son understood how hard it was for me. He said he wanted to drop out and earn money to support our family when he was in junior high school. I knew my daughter had already dropped out of school due to the family situation. My son was very important, so I said, "I won't let you leave school. Even if I go out to beg for food, it's my responsibility to send you to school for an education."

In addition to collecting caterpillar fungus, I also collect *Gentiana macrophylla qinjiu* 'fiddlehead fern'. As a teenager, I carried a spade every fifth lunar month, climbed to the top of a high hill before dawn, and dug until dark. I feared that I would not dig much. I dared not take a break from digging as hard as possible. I didn't even have a drinking cup at the time. I endured thirst. *Qinjiu* is easy to dig. I collected twenty to fifty kilograms a day. I was covered in mud when I finished digging and carried it back home. I

sold it for one RMB per kilogram. I could only earn twenty to fifty RMB a day. It's very physically demanding to dig.

I dug when I was pregnant and carried a sack of *qinjiu* down the mountain with my big belly. I also went with a few female friends to pastoral areas in Sog rdzong County, Rma chu County, and other places in 2013. We took buns and boiled water for the day. On average, I could dig thirty to forty kilograms. I was very satisfied when I earned 300-400 RMB per day, equivalent to ten RMB per kilogram.

When I was about thirty-five, it was popular to build new houses. My father and mother used their savings to build a new house. That was when I relied solely on collecting caterpillar fungus to assist my family. I had to go out to work to help my parents build the house. Since all my childhood pals had married, the first time I went to cut oats in Mdzod dge (Ruo'er gai) County, Sichuan Province, I went with the new daughters-in-law of our village. A herder-owner assigned us to cut his family's oats in different places. One of my female companions and I stayed in a small building in the herder-owner's grassland.

One day, we finished cutting oats in the oats field and rested in our room at night. When we were in bed, we heard something ghostly, like a motorcycle on the roof, frightening us so much that we couldn't sleep. It was very loud. We wondered what the noise was. We thought it was the wind, but the noise seemed far away when we went out to look. When we got inside, it felt like it was on the roof. We both freaked out.

My companion took a stick, poked the ceiling a few times, and shouted, but this didn't help. The sound continued. We both stayed up that night chanting. We went to ask the owner why there was such a noise the next day. He said the sound was supposed to be a ghost. A twenty-year-old man near this building had died in a motorcycle accident. That motorcycle sound was him being a ghost. After hearing this story, we switched to another empty place to cut oats. There was only the sound of water when we went to fetch water during the day. We didn't see anyone. We persisted for two months and then went home with 5,000 RMB each.

I ask village neighbors or relatives in other villages to take me with them if they have work opportunities. Their kindness helps me. I have worked as an assistant laborer in Dar lag County, Mgo log Prefecture, picked wolfberries in Na gor mo County, and gone as far as Zhengzhou City.

When I was in Dar lag County, I worked with my oldest daughter and my son-in-law. I was the cook and assistant worker. Along the side of the highway, we built a concrete wall to prevent landslides. A board used to build the wall weighed thirty to thirty-five kilograms, and we needed to carry the boards from the truck to where the team leader told us to place them.

After unloading the boards, we put concrete on top of each one and then added a layer of boards until there were about twenty layers. It was a hot summer. I constantly sweated when carrying boards. Each of us had to fulfill our individual assigned tasks every day. The job was the same for everyone, regardless of gender. When I stacked boards into ten layers, I couldn't reach or move them. Several times, a board fell and hit my fingertips. Luckily, the *nashi* was nice and said he would take me to the hospital. I didn't go because I thought I could bear it.

About ten women worked initially, but the work was so heavy that only two or three women stayed. The *nashi* realized women did not want to stay and that we didn't have enough cooks, so he told me to cook. In addition to my regular work hours, I also cooked during my breaks. I woke at six a.m. to prepare stir-fry and heat water for fifteen people. I returned to cook and wash the dishes at noon and prepared dinner at six p.m. I was busy and exhausted. Staying in a makeshift mobile room is not too cold, but when it freezes at night, it leaks during the day. It's a good thing the *nashi* paid me 150 RMB a day. I worked for fifty days and made 8,000 RMB.

I don't care if the work is heavy, as long as I can make a lot of money. I don't dare change bosses frequently. If I feel that a boss is short-tempered and scolding, or if I switch around because of bad food, people laugh and say, "This woman has changed many bosses. How demanding!"

I'm afraid of being described like that, so I usually persist.

I don't know how to read or write Chinese. When a boss asks me to do a job, I'll do it as if it were my own, without laziness or complaint. When I go out to work, the bosses have never told me they don't want me. They like and praise me for my good work and want me to continue to work for them.

A woman from my village and I went to Na gor mo City to pick goji berries. When a kilogram of goji berries brought 0.6 RMB, we could sell about 250 kilograms daily. After a month, I earned 10,000 RMB. The boss didn't tell you how much you needed to pick daily. Picking more or less depends on your ability. I wore my raggiest clothes every day and wrapped myself up tightly. Goji trees are full of thorns. After a day of picking, my arms and back ached, and my clothes and fingers were covered with rotten goji berry juice. I had to stand in the sun all day. It was dirty and tiring. Many women, including Chinese and Hui, were picking goji berries. We had a good time during the break. The Chinese boss complimented us on our good work, and I even left my phone number so that we could come and continue to work in the future.

When I returned the following year, I noticed more women picking berries. With the increase in people, there was fierce competition to gather berries. The result was that I picked fewer berries than the year before, and my earnings were not as good as before.

My parents didn't think it was useful for girls to attend school, so I didn't. I couldn't recognize Chinese characters or Tibetan script or speak Chinese well, so I didn't dare look for a job in a big city for a long time. It wasn't until 2019 that people from the township government contacted those of us who had gone out to work and said that there were jobs in Zhengzhou City, Henan Province and that we would be fine even if we didn't know how to read Chinese because, as long as there were people from our place, some could recognize Chinese and translate for us. The work also included food and accommodation; the wage was 150 RMB daily.

After harvest, about fifteen of us went to work together in Zhengzhou City. A few knew Chinese, so I wasn't worried. When we arrived, a Chinese man came to pick us up and took us to the construction site in an underground cave far from the city. We were

digging tunnels. Whenever I went into that dark underground cave, I felt that no enemy would find us if a war went on outside. We lived in dormitories arranged by the company and ate in the cafeteria. At seven a.m., we lined up for roll call and took a bus to the tunnels. Once inside, groups of ten followed a team leader to work.

Inside the tunnels, it was dimly lit. There were smelly sewer smells. We walked in the mud wearing raincoats and waders. My task was to shovel water, mud, and garbage from the tunnels into bags and take them to a place designated by the group leader, where a vehicle picked them up.

There were many workers. Some were responsible for water and electricity, and some did nothing because there was no supervision. The team leader told us when the breaks were. We didn't know the time, so he called the roll when it was time for a break. The leader feared we would get lost because the tunnels were dark and large.

Most workers were local Han. Some entire families worked there and stayed permanently. They were paid very well. Each made at least 10,000 RMB a month. The woman I worked with was from my village and knew more Chinese than I did. I could ask her anything I didn't understand. Sometimes, I was the only one left and didn't understand the team leader. He deliberately bullied me, ordering me to do all the work and calling me an idiot. Everyone had to shower after every day's work and meal, or our wages would be docked. A lot of garbage was in the toilets and bathhouses. The leader once deliberately arranged for me to clean the garbage in the toilets. I noticed the staff cleaning daily, and I wondered why I should clean. If I listened to him, it meant that he had fooled me, so I refused.

Though he was angry, I didn't care. I worked for two months and then returned home in the eleventh lunar month.

It would be endless if I talked about each of my work experiences. I've been slowly forgetting after all these years. For a laborer like me, even if I work very hard every time, as long as I earn money, I am satisfied that I can support and stay with my family. All those work pains are forgotten.

All the money I earned from collecting caterpillar fungus and work was spent on family expenses, such as buying medicine for my husband, paying for two children's schooling, helping my parents build a new house, and so on.

I couldn't afford to buy an expensive Tibetan robe, and if I had minor illnesses, I put up with them until the COVID-19 epidemic, when I was diagnosed with cervical cancer. My body completely fell apart. My periods were erratic. I thought I was getting older and might be experiencing menopause, so I ignored it.

I work hard even if I am on my period. Women around me do the same. No woman in our area takes a break from work because of her period. We think that's shameful and don't let others know. Gynecological exams in town are free every year. I didn't go because I was embarrassed and afraid the doctors would hurt me. It was not until I went to the hospital that I noticed my leukorrhea symptoms were different from those of other women.

I've been hospitalized for the past three years. My husband and children have been caring for me, especially my son, who hasn't had time to take exams and search for a job. I've had two surgeries. The expenses exceeded 300,000 RMB. Chemotherapy was 10,000 RMB each time. Luckily, I don't have to pay much myself. My health insurance reimburses me for a significant portion.

I thought I would die, so I didn't worry about money. I just wanted to be cured, but after surgery, expenses continued for medicines and injections. I couldn't earn money while my body was recovering, so I was a bit worried about money. When I was in the hospital, I thought I had worked very hard to make money, and that's why I was like this. Whenever I collected caterpillar fungus, I lay on the wet ground even if it was snowing and raining. Sometimes, if I couldn't find caterpillar fungus, I was anxious and depressed. Look at me now! I've lost weight and all my hair from chemotherapy. I need help standing and sitting, and sometimes I can't eat.

The whole village says no family has suffered more than ours. Though others have difficulty, none are sick. They are healthy and can still earn money. My husband and I are both ill and can't

make money. To get a *dibao* allowance¹ from the government, I tearfully begged the village headman to explain our family situation. He reluctantly agreed because he had already chosen a few families with whom he had a good relationship. Ordinary people like me want a certificate of poverty from that government employee. They are willing to write a certificate after cigarettes or liquor are bought for them.

As we waited for the government people to inspect my family's hospitalization certificate and ask me about my income and expenses, the village Party Secretary warned, "Be careful what you say, and don't cause trouble."

I'm helpless at times.

A female relative in another village is in my situation. That woman's husband was imprisoned for seven or eight years for wrongdoing. That woman works by herself to support the family. She could have divorced and left her husband's family with her kids, but she endured it so the children had a father. We went out to work together. I know her work experience. She has been to Mgo log Prefecture to collect caterpillar fungus, to a factory in Na gor mo City, and worked in Zi ling City.

When she worked in Zi ling, her bosses did not pay her, so she went to the Labor Bureau to sue them, eventually receiving 13,000 RMB. She used this money for a government loan to build a new house. When we worked together, we sometimes had a meal together. She didn't want to eat in a restaurant, said she didn't like restaurant food, and would rather eat instant noodles. I knew she wanted to save money.

When I was happy that she was moving to a new house this year, she fell off a ladder to the roof one morning. I visited her in the hospital when I heard about it. Fortunately, her spine was not completely broken. Her injured spine will heal with recuperation.

She told me the accident was because she worked outside all year, and her son was in school. No one in the family worshiped

¹ *Dibao* households receive a minimum subsistence allowance from the government because they have no labor force due to severe disability or illness.

the mountain deity punctually every day, so she was punished. She is now in bed and needs six months of treatment. As an injured woman in a low-income family, she must seek help from others. Thankfully, her son received 100,000 RMB by going door-to-door to people all over the township and through online assistance. When her son said he needed to post her situation online for help, she replied, "I agree as long as you're not ashamed."

When she received those donations, she cried for a long time and then asked me to spend 10,000 RMB to light lamps for blessings in the village *ma Ni khang* and the monastery. She said, "I don't know what bad things I did in my last life. I'm here to redeem myself in this life. I can't die. My husband and son have no one to care for them. The house has just been built and isn't finished. I can't die."

CONCLUSION

Based on semi-structured interviews, the article describes the real-life experiences of five illiterate women in Gshong yul Tibetan Village who worked in agriculture and outside the home. The main labor was collecting caterpillar fungus and construction labor. In contrast to male workers, female workers are busy with home chores such as childrearing, caring for elders, cooking, farming, working with their husbands, and living their inferior socio-cultural status as daughters-in-law. Consequently, for these illiterate Tibetan women, migrant work is an economic activity and a temporary freedom from their usual identity.

The rise of the market economy, the influence of family patriarchy, and the division of gender roles in traditional society have created the low social status of women in villages for a long time. Women must obey their parents, husbands, and in-laws in significant family matters. For example, their marriages were arranged by their parents. The primary reason women work outside the home is to earn money for their families. For young women, working outside is a way to escape their in-laws and temporarily gain personal freedom. For example, in the case of Mtsho mo (b. 1988), she must serve a large family daily and lacks

the freedom to wear make-up and clothes she likes. Working outside gives her the freedom to be herself for a short time. She can rest, sleep, go shopping, wear what she wants, and make-up when she is off work and is not judged by her in-laws and villagers. Some women find value in their work. For example, Me tog said that when she could support her family on her own without the help of a man. She embodied the value she created by earning money through work.

The geographical mobility of Tibetan female migrant workers in Gshong yul Village shows the impact and limitations of their geographical and ethnic identities. They lack policy guidance from the State and formal professional intermediary organizations. They access a spontaneous, informal organization based on family connections and geographic identity, providing mutual help and transferring information among members within the village. Female villagers often follow their husbands, relatives, or family members first, and then their familiar female companions, seeking a sense of security and belonging. These women have no schooling. The consequence was a very limited ability in the Chinese language, leading to work challenges. They can only speak Amdo Tibetan and a rudimentary Qinghai Chinese. For this reason, they are more inclined towards employment in Tibetan towns and cities with large Tibetan populations, where they can adapt. Although a few women have gone to work in cities farther away, the differences in culture, climate, and forms of work have made it difficult. They had no intention of working there again. Women's submissiveness led to the choice of industries concentrated in labor-intensive fields with a strong labor force, low skill requirements, and low income. They mainly concentrate on simple manual labor, such as collecting caterpillar fungus, *Gentiana*, and ferns, as well as serving as assistant workers on construction sites. Male workers' wages were generally higher than those of female workers, partly due to greater physical strength.

Based on the life narratives of five Tibetan women in Gshong yul Village and their labor experiences, these women face marginalization in both their families and work

environments. Village culture requires that a daughter-in-law live with her husband's family and serve the elders, children, and her husband; undertake agricultural work and household chores; and earn income by working, even if the money she earns must be given to male family elders or her husband.

These five female workers lacked adequate protection for their labor rights and benefits in the labor market, including the absence of labor contracts, working while pregnant, and unpaid wages. Discrimination by their employers was based on their gender and physical strength. They lived in crowded, makeshift dormitories or substandard tents, were assigned intense labor, received a monotonous diet, often breathed in cement dust and dirt detrimental to their health, and had limited proficiency in the Chinese language, leading to work challenges. Two female workers mentioned they were abused by their jealous husbands, stemming from interaction with other males during work.

Working outside their home community was vital for these five female workers to support their families financially, despite the challenging work environment. Zi ling's year-round employment allowed Lha mo (b. 1994) to earn almost 60,000 RMB, significantly improving her family's living conditions. With this income, they purchased meat and various vegetables, built a new house, and bought a car. Working outside their community was a crucial economic activity for these Tibetan women.

The five consultants were from a generation before enforced school attendance. Their families saw no need for them to attend school. Instead, marriage and having children were considered important. Compared to educated young Tibetan women with more life choices, the thoughts and behaviors of these five women were restricted by their families' and communities' struggles to fulfill their aspirations. Once married, they lived with their husbands' families and spent their time and energy on matters concerning the family. Migrant work allowed them to learn from the outside world and gain temporary freedom from their husbands' homes while demonstrating their ability to earn money.

The status of local Tibetan female workers was inferior to that of males in their families and the workplace. They were expected to care for family members and perform all household chores as daughters-in-law. The five reports provide detailed and descriptive accounts that encompass key themes, including marriage, discrimination, prejudice, and workplace living conditions. Their narratives reveal pronounced emotional ambivalence. Their experiences as migrant workers as they reflect on their struggle for autonomy through economic participation are marked by fear, hardship, and despair. This tension reflects the complex adaptation strategies of illiterate Tibetan women in the process of modernization.

Exploring the life stories and labor migration process of five Tibetan female workers in Gshong yul Community sheds light on A mdo Tibetan women in the workforce. This study contends that Tibetan female workers' motivations, experiences, and encountered challenges are closely tied to her gender roles and family background. This contributes to our understanding of Tibetan female workers and has broad implications for gender studies, labor migration studies, and predicaments faced by A mdo Tibetan women today.

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TIBETAN TERMS

'bar tshang འབར་ཚང་།
 a chen gangs rgyal ཨ་ཚན་གངས་རྒྱལ།
 bde skyid བདེ་སྦྱིད།
 bla brang ལྷ་བང་།
 brag dkar བྲག་དཀར།
 bsang chu བསང་ཆུ།
 chu ka, khri ka ལུ་ཀ་ ཀྲི་ཀ།
 dbus gtsang དབུས་གཙང་།
 dkar mdzes དཀར་མཛེས།
 dred tshang རྩེད་ཚང་།
 gcan tsha གཅན་ཚ།
 gser rta གཤེར་རྟ།
 khams ཁམས།
 lha mo ལྷ་མོ།
 lo sar ལོ་སར།
 ma Ni མ་ཤེ།
 mdzo rgan ra bar མཛོ་རྟན་ར་བར།
 me tog མེ་ཏོག།
 mtsho byang མཚོ་བྱང་།
 mtsho sngon མཚོ་སྔོན།
 na gor mo ན་གོར་མོ།
 rgan gya རྟན་གྲ།
 rma chu རྩ་ཆུ།
 ru ma byung རུ་མ་བྱུང་།
 sha ba ཤ་བ།
 sha ba tsho ba ཤ་བ་ཚོ་བ།
 sog rdzong སོག་རྫོང་།
 stag lha khri སྟག་ལྷ་ཀྲི།
 them chen ཐེམ་ཚེན།
 yu mo ཡུ་མོ།
 Salar srang ཟ་ལར་སྲིང་།
 zi ling ཟི་ལིང་།

'brong ri dgon pa འབྲོང་རི་དགོན་པ།
 a mdo ཨ་མདོ།
 bis mdo བེས་མདོ།
 bla ma ལྷ་མ།
 brag sne nang བྲག་སྡེ་ནང་།
 chu dmar leb ཆུ་དམར་ལེབ།
 dar lag དར་ལག།
 dga' bde དགའ་བདེ།
 dp'a lung དཔའ་ལུང་།
 ed bzhed ཨེད་བཞེད།
 gcig sgril གཅིག་སྦྱིལ།
 gshong yul གཤོང་ཡུལ།
 klu mo thang ལུ་མོ་ཐང་།
 lha sa ལྷ་ས།
 ma Ni khang མ་ཤེ་ཁང་།
 mdo la མདོ་ལ།
 mdzod dge མཛོད་དགེ།
 mgo log མགོ་ལོག།
 mtsho mo མཚོ་མོ།
 mtsho sngon po མཚོ་སྔོན་པོ།
 rebgong རེབ་གོང་།
 rgya ri ma sgang ལྷ་རི་མ་སྐང་།
 rma stod རྩ་སྟོད།
 sgrol ma སྦྱོལ་མ།
 sha ba tshang ཤ་བ་ཚང་།
 skye dgu mdo སྐྱེ་དགུ་མདོ།
 srung སྲུང་།
 the ge ཐེ་གེ།
 ya rdzi ཡ།རྩེ།
 yul shul ཡུལ་ཤུལ།
 zhor las ཚོར་ལས།

CHINESE TERMS

Dari 达日	<i>dibao</i> 低保
Gande 甘德	Ganjia 甘加
Gannan 甘南	Ganzi 甘孜
Ge'ermu 格尔木	<i>goji</i> 枸杞
<i>gongshe</i> 公社	Haibei 海北
Haixi 海西	Han 汉
Henan 河南	Hongqi 红旗
Hualong 化隆	Huashixia 花石峡
Hui 回	Jiangsu 江苏
Jianzha 尖扎	Jiegu 结古
Jiezi 街子	Jiuzhi 久治
Kekexili 可可西里	Lanzhou 兰州
Maduo 玛多	Mgo log 果洛
<i>mu</i> 亩	<i>nashi</i> 纳什
Ningxia 宁夏	Qilian 祁连
Qinghai 青海	<i>qinjiu</i> 秦艽
Qumalai 曲麻莱	Rimaxiong 日麻雄
Ruo'er gai 若尔盖	Sala 撒拉
Seda 色达	Shanghai 上海
Shanxi 陕西	Sichuan 四川
Suzhou 苏州	Tianjun 天峻
Tongren 同仁	Wanda 万达
Wendou 文都	Xi'an 西安
Xiahe 夏河	Xiangyu 相玉
Ximen 西门	Xinghai 兴海
Xining 西宁	Xunhua 循化
Yinchuan 银川	Yushu 玉树
Zhengzhou 郑州	